

FOCCUS

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D2.1: Data Reports

WP2: New insight of high-resolution coastal observations

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Glossary and abbreviations

BC	Brockmann Consult
BGC	Biogeochemical
CF	Climate Forecast (Convention for NetCDF)
CNR	National Research Council (Italy)
DPV	Data Product Validation
DMI	Danish Meteorological Institute
DCSM	Delft3D Coastal Systems Model
EO	Earth Observation
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ESC	Environmental and Societal Challenges
FRM	Fiducial Reference Measurements
FOCCUS	Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean for Copernicus users
HABs	Harmful Algal Blooms
HEREON	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon
HR	High-Resolution
HFR	High-Frequency Radar
IFREMER	French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea
ISAR	Infrared Sea surface temperature Autonomous Radiometer
MHWs	Marine Heatwaves
MHD	Marine Hydrographic Directorate (Romania)
MET.NO	Norwegian Meteorological Institute
MSI	MultiSpectral Instrument
NERSC	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (Norway)
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NOC	National Oceanography Centre (UK)
NW	North West
ODP	Operational Data Product
OGCM	Ocean Global Circulation Model
OLCI	Ocean and Land Colour Instrument
PDPD	Proof of concept Data Product
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
PU	Public
PUM	Product User Manual
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
RBINS	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
S2	Sentinel-2
S3	Sentinel-3
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SDB	Satellite-Derived Bathymetry
SAV	Submerged Aquatic Vegetation
SCHISM	Semi-implicit Cross-scale Hydrosience Integrated System Model
SOCIB	Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TWL	Total Water level
WP	Work Package
WW3	WaveWatch III®
XBEACH	Cross-shore Beach Dynamics Model

1. Executive summary

The **FOCCUS project** (<https://foccus-project.eu/>) aims to enhance coastal ocean observation and forecasting for Copernicus users by designing and implementing a range of high-resolution data products. The **work package 2 (WP)** focuses on improving pan-European **innovative coastal ocean observations** in response to society and EU policy needs in the context of climate change.

The **data products** of innovative coastal observations, **summarised in Table 1**, will be integrated in coastal modelling and coastal applications work packages to address pressing environmental and societal challenges (ESC).

This report **provides** an overview of **all data products** that are being designed and further developed in all tasks (2.1, 2.2 and 2.3) from WP2 ([table 1](#)), comprising operational data products (**ODPs**) and proof of concept data products (**PDPDs**) as well as data product validation (**DPV**) across various domains. Notable examples include:

- **Sea level products** derived from satellite altimetry, offering valuable insights into coastal dynamics and sea level rise.
- **High-resolution sea surface temperature** products are crucial for understanding marine heatwaves and ecosystem health.
- **Innovative products** like **sea ice change** detection and **harmful algal bloom** probability maps utilising advanced technologies and machine learning approaches.
- **Data fusion** techniques to create comprehensive **surface current datasets**.
- **Beach monitoring and morphodynamic process products** supporting coastal erosion management and resilience planning.

Coastal and river data have also been included in sections 2 and 3 of this deliverable. However, detailed inventories will be provided in the D2.3 (to be delivered on the 30th of June 2025).

The **coastal data** inventory will initially include JERICO data and in-situ products of the Copernicus Marine Service, starting with the French coastal data of the ILICO RI. Other EU coastal data for automatic measurements and physical and biogeochemical parameters will be included. Relevant metadata will be completed for each platform, including platform type, creator, country, network/RI/programme/project, geographical position, parameter, depth, period. This initial inventory will be reviewed and enhanced by coastal experts and data managers.

The **river data** inventory will include major rivers across different sea basins (e.g. Atlantic Ocean, Baltic Sea, Black Sea and Mediterranean Sea), data availability, and water discharge levels. It will list platform name, provider agency, URL (if available), coordinates, latest data and key variables (e.g. flow rate, total suspended matter, nutrients - nitrogen and phosphorus -, sediments).

The **document is structured** to provide a comprehensive overview of coastal data products. **Section 2** offers an initial list ([table 1](#)), expanded upon in later sections. [Section 3](#) gives a brief description of each data product, while [section 4](#) delves into methodology, metadata and use cases. The document emphasises standardised formats (e.g. NetCDF) and comprehensive metadata ([Annex I](#)) to facilitate data integration and sharing. [Annex II](#) includes the Key Performance Indicators of this WP to facilitate the review process. Additionally, a glossary and abbreviations section is included for clarity.

2. Data products

[Table 1](#) summarises the **list of data products** to be designed in the context of the WP2 that will be used in downstream WPs of coastal models (WP 6/7) and coastal applications (WP 8/9). Each data product is linked to the corresponding data sheet, available in [section 3](#) and the data description from [section 4](#).

Overall, [table 1](#) serves as a concise overview of the data products under development, their key characteristics, and how they fit into the broader project goals of supporting coastal modelling and applications.

Table 1.- High-resolution coastal observations data products.

#	Task	Data product (section 3)	Lead	Coverage (area of interest)	Format	Expected outcome	Related coastal model	Related coastal application	Description (section 4)
1.	2.1.1	Sea level	CLS	European seas (Mediterranean, Black Sea, Atlantic up to 66°N, Baltic) ¹	netCDF	ODP ² (TRL=5) Reprocessing	WMOP	ESC2 - Multi-use of off-shore installations ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding ESC3 - Combating degradation of ecosystems	Section 4.1
2.	2.1.1	Sea surface temperature	CNR	North Adriatic Sea	netCDF	ODP (TRL=5) Novel data product development	AdrFS	ESC3 - Natural hazards and extreme events (MHWs) ESC3 - Combating degradation of ecosystems	Section 4.2
3.	2.1.1	Sea ice changes	NERSC	Arctic Ocean (Svalbard, Greenland coastal zone)	netCDF	ODP (TRL=5) Experimental	TOPAZ, NORKYST	ESC1 - Natural hazards and extreme events in coastal areas.	Section 4.3
4.	2.1.2	HR total surface currents	NERSC	Norwegian coastal zone	netCDF	ODP (TRL=6)	Norkyst (MET.NO/NERSC) WMOP (SOCIB)	ESC1 - Pollution hazard ESC2 - Multi-use of off-shore installations ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding	Section 4.4

¹ Sentinel-6 data (up to 66° N) and SWOT nadir data (up to 78° N).

² ODP = Operational Data Product.

5.	2.1.3	BGC anomalies & trends	CNR	North Adriatic Sea	netCDF	ODP (TRL=5) Reprocessing	New E-HYPE version DCSM (Deltares)	ESC1 - Pollution hazard ESC1 - Coastal erosion ESC3 - Combating degradation of ecosystems	Section 4.5
6.	2.1.3	Seagrass and macroalgae maps	BC	German Bight, Western Mediterranean (Balearic Sea)	netCDF	ODP (TRL=5)	WW3 model SCHISM-WWM-X BEACH GCOAST-GB (HEREON) DCSM (Deltares)	ESC1 - Pollution hazard ESC1 - Coastal erosion ESC2 - Multi-use of off-shore installations ESC3-Combating ecosystem degradation ESC3 - low-trophic level aquaculture	Section 4.6
7.	2.1.4	Beach monitoring products	SOCIB	Western Mediterranean (Balearic Sea) Black Sea (NW) Atlantic Ocean (Lisbon coastal zone)	Report (pdf) and netCDF, SHP, example	PDPD ³ (TRL=5)	GCOAST-BS	ESC1 - Coastal erosion ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding	Section 4.7
8.	2.2.1	Ocean currents	CLS	Mediterranean Sea (western)	netCDF	PDPD (TRL=5)	WMOP (SOCIB)	ESC1 - Pollution hazard ESC2 - Multi-use of off-shore installations ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding	Section 4.8
9.	2.2.1	HABs probability maps	NERSC	Norwegian coastal zone	netCDF	ODP (TRL=6)	Norkyst (MET.NO/NERSC) TOPAZ	ESC1 - Pollution hazard ESC2 - Aquaculture/fisheries/energy sector ESC3-Combating ecosystem degradation	Section 4.9
10.	2.2.1	Inland-marine water connectivity	CNR	Adriatic Sea coastal zone (Po River Delta)	Report (pdf)	PDPD (TRL=5) Identification of fluvial/marine	AdrFS??	ESC1 - Pollution hazard ESC1 - Coastal erosion ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding	Section 4.10

³ PDPD = Preparation of the data product development

						spectral signatures			
11.	2.2.2	Sea level and currents	NERSC	Atlantic: NW European Shelf; Atlantic; Nordic Seas, Norwegian coast	netCDF	DPV ⁴ (TRL=5)	TOPAZ, Norkyst	ESC1 - Management and protection of coastal area ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding	Section 4.11
12.	2.2.2	FRM for OC and SST radiometer obs	CNR	Adriatic Sea coastal zone (Po River Delta) North Sea ()	Report (pdf) and NetCDF example	DPV	AdrFS	ESC1 - Pollution hazard ESC1 - Coastal erosion ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding	Section 4.12
13.	2.3.1	Beach morphodynamic processes	SOCIB	Western Mediterranean (Balearic Sea) Black Sea (NW) Atlantic Ocean (Lisbon coastal zone) Southern North Sea	Report (pdf) and NetCDF example	PDPD (TRL=X)		ESC1 - Coastal erosion ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding	Section 4.13
14.	2.3.2	Coastal data	Ifremer	Pan-European, Global Ocean	netCDF	Inventory (D2.3)	Lazio WMOP (SOCIB)	ESC1, ESC2, ESC3 ESC3 - Natural hazards and extreme events (MHWs)	Not applicable
15.	2.3.3	River data	+ATLANTIC	Atlantic: Iberia-Biscay-Ireland Mediterranean Sea Baltic Sea Black Sea Atlantic: NW European Shelf Atlantic: Iberia-Biscay-Ireland	netCDF	Inventory (D2.3)	Waves and storm surge forecasts. New E-HYPE version WMOP (SOCIB) LisOcean MOHID (+ATLANTIC)	ESC1 - Pollution Hazard ESC2-Multi-use offshore wind farms with low-trophic level aquaculture. ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding	Not applicable

ESC1= Management and protection of the coastal area; ESC2=Enhance Blue Economy; ESC3= Hazards and resilience to climate change.

⁴ DPV = Data Product Validation.

3. Data products sheets

This section includes **data sheets** for each **data product** designed in WP2 (as listed in [table 1](#)), detailing the final product, including a brief description, observing platform, spatial and temporal extent and resolution, variables, feature type, update frequency, format and the provider.

- By **improving remote sensing techniques**, WP2 aims to enhance our understanding of coastal processes and support decision-making in climate monitoring, weather forecasting, marine services, and ocean health assessments, providing the following key coastal data products:
 - **Coastal sea level**: enhancing altimetry data processing for improved measurements.
 - **Sea surface temperature**: developing high-resolution products.
 - **Landfast ice**: classified using Sentinel-1 SAR images.
 - **Ocean surface currents**: retrieved high-resolution data from Sentinel-1 SAR.
 - **Biogeochemical products and indicators**: generated from Sentinel-2 & 3 data.
 - **Seagrass and macroalgae mapping**: improved using Sentinel-2.
 - **Beach monitoring products**: designed using various data sources (video monitoring, Coastsnap, in-situ measurements, etc.).
- By **innovating in data fusion and satellite calibration/validation** WP2 aims to deliver:
 - **High-resolution ocean surface current products**: Developed by fusing data from various sensors, such as satellites, high-frequency (HF) radar, and in-situ platforms.
 - **Harmful algal Blooms (HABs) probability maps**: Created for Norwegian coastal areas by combining multi-source data.
 - **Inland-marine water connectivity assessments**: Conducted using Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 data, along with in-situ radiometry.
 - **Satellite calibration and validation**: Achieved through the combined use of Argo floats, gliders and other platforms.
 - **Ocean colour and sea surface temperature validation**: Performed using coastal fiducial reference measurements (FRM), providing essential ground truth data.
- By **applying artificial intelligence and improving data traceability** and tracking, WP2:
 - Provides **beach morphodynamic processes data products** (e.g. shoreline changes, seagrass wracks and satellite-derived bathymetry) from imagery using AI techniques.
 - Improves traceability and tracking of **in-situ coastal and river data**: within European marine data services.

3.1. Sea level

Table 2.- Sea level data product sheet

⁵ In all tables, latitude is given in degrees north and longitude in degrees east.

3.2. Sea surface temperature (SST)

Table 3.- Sea surface temperature (SST) data product sheet

SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE

DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION

Full Name	Merged multi-sensor (L3S) SST
Description	Regional, daily, merged high-resolution (~1 km) multi-sensor (level-3S, L3S) SST product (from Sentinel-3, MetOp, SNPP, NOAA-20) over specific coastal regions. Pioneering studies will be pursued to investigate potential retrieval of SST from hyper spatial resolution satellite sensors in transitional/estuarine waters.
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	North Adriatic Sea
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [43.47° to 44.30°] · Lon [12.22° to 13.05°]
Time Span	From 01/01/2020 to 31/12/2020
Spatial resolution	1km x 1km
Temporal resolution	Daily
Variables	Sea Surface Temperature
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency	Yearly
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	CNR
Improvement	Application of a new flag/masking scheme over coastal regions to display reliable pixels near the coastline. Exploitation of high-spatial resolution missions/sensor(s) synergy. Additional exploitation of SST retrieved from a new sensor, i.e. ECOSTRESS (not committed in the project)
External Link	N/A

3.3. Sea ice changes

Table 4.- Sea Ice data product sheet

SEA ICE

DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION

Full Name	Land fast ice
Description	Land fast ice detected on sequential SAR imagery by low ice drift speed
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	Arctic Ocean
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [70° to 83°] · Lon [-30° to 30°]
Time Span	From 01/10/2019 to 01/04/2020
Spatial resolution	100 m x 100 m
Temporal resolution	Irregular (depending on SAR coverage)
Variables	Sea ice
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency	None
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	NERSC
Improvement	Combining unique sea-ice dynamics in neXtSIM and the basal stress formulation.
External Link	N/A

3.4. High-resolution total surface currents

Table 5.- High-resolution total surface currents data product sheet

SURFACE CURRENT RADIAL VELOCITY	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	High-Resolution Total Surface Currents
Description	Total Ocean Surface (TSC) Current Radial Velocity (RVL) derived from Doppler Centroid Anomaly acquired by Sentinel-1A/B SAR. Calibration is applied based on the land-based signal to correct instrumental errors. The wind- and wave-induced signal is removed using empirical geophysical model function based on auxiliary wind/wave model fields.
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	Norwegian Coastal Zone
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [56 to 72] · Lon [1 to 29]
Time Span	From 15/05/2019 to 31/12/2022
Spatial resolution	1 km x 1 km
Temporal resolution	Irregular; Instantaneous
Variables	Surface Current Radial Velocity
Feature type	Swath
Update frequency	Daily
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	NERSC
Improvement	The new direct observations of the high-resolution coastal ocean surface current based on the auxiliary CMEMS information
External Link	https://www.worldoceanicirculation.org/Products#/metadata/eb10fc04-0d51-42b5-8788-f9b40130c2a1

3.5. Bio-geo-chemical (BGC) anomalies and trends

3.5.1 BGC anomalies and trends - CNR

Table 6.- Biogeochemical anomalies and trends data product sheet

BIOGEOCHEMICAL ANOMALIES AND TRENDS	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	Full-Resolution (300 m) surface Chlorophyll-a and Total Suspended Matter concentration
Description	Weekly Chlorophyll-a and Total Suspended Matter concentrations at the sea surface from S3-OLCI time series and related weekly anomalies and statistical trends
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	North Adriatic Sea
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [43.4708° to 44.2958°] · Lon [12.2208° to 13.0458°]
Time Span	From 01/01/2019 to 31/12/2023
Spatial resolution	300 m x 300 m
Temporal resolution	Weekly; Yearly
Variables	Chlorophyll-a Total Suspended Matter concentration
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency / Latency	Yearly
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	CNR
Improvement	Full-resolution Sentinel3-OLCI products and provisioning of statistical analyses suitable for coastal applications
External Link/Access channel	N/A

3.5.2 BGC multisensor coastal product - BC

Table 7.- High-Resolution surface Chlorophyll-a concentration and Turbidity data product sheet

MultiRes Product provided by D. Van der Zande, RBINS	
BIOGEOCHEMICAL ANOMALIES AND TRENDS	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	High-Resolution surface Chlorophyll-a concentration and Turbidity
Description	Daily Chlorophyll-a concentration and Turbidity derived from S2-MSI and S3-OLCI data (merged product)
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	German Bight; Black Sea; Atlantic; Iberia-Biscay-Ireland
Spatial coverage	Coastal area German Bight · Lat [52° to 56.33°] · Lon [4.66° to 9.5°] Coastal area Black Sea · Lat [40° to 48°] · Lon [26.5° to 42°] Coastal area Atlantic: Iberia-Biscay-Ireland · Lat [26° to 48°] · Lon [-20° to -5.61°]
Time Span	From 01/01/2020 to 31/12/2024
Spatial resolution	100 m x 100 m
Temporal resolution	Daily; Monthly
Variables	Chlorophyll-a concentration: Turbidity
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency / Latency	Monthly
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	BC
Improvement	Multi-sensor merged product between Sentinel-2 MSI and Sentinel-3 OLCI acquisitions; alignment of OC parameters and merging procedure using DINEOF (Multi-Res Approach developed by RBINS and University of Liège). This product will build on existing CMS products: high resolution coastal product (HROC) and OLCI products (Globcolour and OC_BLK_BGC).
External Link/Access channel	N/A

3.6. Seagrass and macroalgae

3.6.1 Emerged seagrass and macroalgae

Table 8.- Emerged seagrass and macroalgae data product sheet

SEAGRASS AND MACROALGAE	
Data product information	
Full Name	Emerged seagrass and macroalgae
Description	Mapping of emerged seagrass and macroalgae in the intertidal, using advanced methods for habitat mapping from Sentinel-2
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	German Bight
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [53.88° to 55.68°] · Lon [8° to 9.13°]
Time Span	From 2020 to 2023
Spatial resolution	10 m x 10 m (30 m x 30 m)
Temporal resolution	Yearly
Variables	ndvivegetation_percent_covern_obs
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency / Latency	Yearly
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	BCCNR
Improvement	This new product, developed within the FOCCUS project, uses advanced methods to map intertidal aquatic vegetation during low-tide conditions from Sentinel-2 data based on spectral indices and temporal aggregation. The product will be generated during the annual seasonal peak of vegetation (summer)
External Link/Access channel	N/A

3.6.2 Submerged seagrass and macroalgae

Table 9.- Submerged seagrass and macroalgae data product sheet

SEAGRASS AND MACROALGAE	
Data product information	
Full Name	Submerged Aquatic Vegetation
Description	Mapping of subtidal seagrass and macroalgae, using advanced methods for habitat mapping from Sentinel-2
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	Balearic Islands
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [38.6° to 40.2°] · Lon [1.0° to 4.4°]
Time Span	2019
Spatial resolution	10 m x 10 m
Temporal resolution	Yearly
Variables	Submerged aquatic vegetation; number of available observations
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency / Latency	Yearly
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	BC; CNR
Improvement	DISCLAIMER: This is a novel product for a new Copernicus Service element which is being developed in the course of FOCCUS. Novel development and implementation of advanced methods for mapping of submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV) from Sentinel-2 data.
External Link/Access channel	N/A

3.7. Beach monitoring

3.7.1. High-resolution topobathymetries

Table 10.- Topobathymetries data product sheet

HIGH-RESOLUTION TOPOBATHYMETRIES	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	High-resolution coastal topobathymetries
Description	Periodic beach topography and shallow water bathymetry from the Balearic Islands (3 beaches) and the Romanian coastal area. Sand level measurements covering the entire beach system (from approximately +2 m to -15 m) delivered as interpolated grids and multipoints.
Source	In-situ observations
Area or Geographical coverage	Balearic Islands; Black Sea
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [39.25° to 40.10°] · Lon [2.30° to 4.45°]; Lat [43.74° to 45.15°] · Lon [28.55° to 29.80°]
Time Span	From 2011 to 2024
Spatial resolution	10 m x 10 m (interpolated grid) and irregular (multipoints ~ 1 m x 1 m)
Temporal resolution	Irregular
Variables	X, Y, Z
Feature type	Grid; MultiPoint
Update frequency	Yearly
Format	NetCDF-4; .shp
Provider	SOCIB; MHD
Improvement	Enhanced temporal and spatial resolution; expert supervised quality control
External Link	FOCCUS T2.1.4 Report - (section 6.3.2) Topobathymetries

3.7.2. Waves

Table 11.- Waves data product sheet

WAVES

DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION

Full Name	Wave parameters (in-situ)
Description	Hourly wave conditions data from the Balearic Islands spans 2011-2024 and includes in-situ observations from wave buoys and current profilers at specific coastal locations. Data was processed to level L2 and is provided in NetCDF-4 format.
Source	In-situ observations (Wave Buoy; Current Profiler)
Area or Geographical coverage	Balearic Islands
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [39.25° to 40.10°] · Lon [2.30° to 4.45°]; Lat [43.74° to 45.15°] · Lon [28.55° to 29.80°]
Time Span	From 2011 to 2024
Spatial resolution	Time series at a specific location.
Temporal resolution	Hourly
Variables	Wave
Feature type	Timeseries
Update frequency	Hourly (RT Buoy); Yearly(Current profiler)
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	SOCIB
Improvement	L0/L1 to L2 processing level;
External Link	FOCCUS T2.1.4 Report - (section 6.3.3) Waves

3.7.3. Sea level

Table 12.- Sea level data product sheet

SEA LEVEL	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	Sea Level - Real-Time / Near Real-Time Values
Description	This dataset provides near real-time sea level observations from tide gauges in the Balearic Islands and the Black Sea, collected from 2011 to 2024 and 2021 to 2024, respectively. It includes the water surface height above specific datum measurements at sub-hourly and hourly resolutions, processed and standardised by SOCIB and DHM.
Source	In-situ observations
Area or Geographical coverage	Balearic Islands; Black Sea
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [39.25° to 40.10°] · Lon [2.30° to 4.45°]; Lat [43.74° to 45.15°] · Lon [28.55° to 29.80°]
Time Span	2011 to 2024; From 2021 to 2024.
Spatial resolution	Time series at a specific location.
Temporal resolution	Sub-hourly; Daily
Variables	Sea surface height; Sea level pressure; ancillary variables
Feature type	Point
Update frequency	Hourly; 6 Minutes
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	SOCIB; MHD
Improvement	Data collection, quality control and standardisation.
External Link	SOCIB tide gauges , DHM tide gauges , FOCCUS T2.1.4 Report - (section 6.3.4) SeaLevel

3.7.4. Shoreline position

Table 13.- Shorelines data product sheet

SHORELINES	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	Shoreline position
Description	High-resolution shoreline positions measured in-situ with RTK (Real-Time Kinematic) and image derived ones from beach imaging systems products (manually digitised). In the Balearic Islands (5 monitored beaches) and the Black Sea (Romanian coastal area) from 2011 to 2024. Data were collected, quality-controlled and spatially resolved to 1-3 m accuracy.
Source	In-situ observations Beach monitoring imagery
Area or Geographical coverage	Balearic Islands; Black Sea
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [39.25° to 40.10°] · Lon [2.30° to 4.45°]; Lat [43.74° to 45.15°] · Lon [28.55° to 29.80°]
Time Span	From 2011 to 2024
Spatial resolution	1 to 3 m
Temporal resolution	Irregular
Variables	X, Y, Z
Feature type	MultiPoint
Update frequency	Yearly
Format	.shp
Provider	SOCIB; MHD
Improvement	Data collection, spatial resolution, coverage, expert supervision and quality control.
External Link	FOCCUS T2.1.4 Report - (section 6.3.1) Shorelines

3.7.5. Total water level

Table 14.- Total water level data product sheet

Total Water Level	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	Total Water Level (TWL)
Description	The Total Water Level (TWL) dataset for the Portuguese continental coast provides an hourly time series from 1994 to 2022. The TWL is computed using a linear summation equation that considers the wave runup, astronomical tides, storm surges and sea level anomalies to model coastal water levels. By integrating multiple dynamic components, the TWL dataset provides a comprehensive insight of coastal exposure to extreme events such as flooding and overtopping, supporting coastal risk management.
Source	Satellite; In-situ observations; Reanalysis
Area or Geographical coverage	Portugal coast
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [36.9° to 41.9°] · Lon [-9.51° to -7.40°]
Time Span	From 1994 to 2022
Spatial resolution	Time series at a specific locations along the coast
Temporal resolution	Hourly
Variables	X, Y, Z
Feature type	Timeseries
Update frequency	Biannual
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	+ATLANTIC
Improvement	TWL is essential for assessing potential coastal erosion and flooding risks.
External Link	Link to subsection f) of Section 6.3.5. in “FOCCUS T2.1.4 Report (section 6.3.5)”

3.8. Surface currents

Table 15.- Surface currents data product sheet

SURFACE CURRENTS

DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION

Full Name	Surface gridded total currents from data fusion
Description	Total surface currents calculated from data fusion technique (machine learning approach). Learning will be performed on model data and inference on real observations (L3/L4 sea level, satellite SST, SSS, winds). HF radar will be used for validation.
Source	Machine Learning model
Area or Geographical coverage	Mediterranean Sea (western sub-basin)
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Three 50x50km boxes around HFR positions (chosen among DeltaEbro, Ibiza, Tirlig, CALYPSO) in western Mediterranean Sea
Time Span	From 01/01/2024 to 30/12/2024
Spatial resolution	5kmx5km
Temporal resolution	Hourly
Variables	Velocity
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency	None
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	CLS
Improvement	Merging of multi-data sources and exploring machine learning approach to retrieve total surface currents
External Link	N/A

3.9. Harmful algal blooms (HABs) probability

Table 16.- Harmful algae blooms probability data product sheet

HAB PROBABILITY

Data product information

Full Name	Harmful algae bloom (HAB) probability
Description	The probability of detecting toxic algae in surface waters for a given temperature, mixed layer depth, salinity, and photosynthetic available radiation. Probability is estimated using machine learning models. The toxic algae are: <i>Alexandrium</i> spp., <i>Alexandrium tamarensis</i> group, <i>Dinophysis acuta</i> , <i>Dinophysis acuminata</i> , <i>Dinophysis norvegica</i> , <i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> spp., <i>Protoceratium reticulatum</i> , and <i>Azadinium spinosum</i> .
Source	Machine learning model
Area or Geographical coverage	Norwegian coastal zone
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [+57° to +72°] · Lon [+2° to +34°]
Time Span	From 01/01/2023 to 31/12/2023
Spatial resolution	4km x 4km
Temporal resolution	Weekly
Variables	HAB probability
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency / Latency	Monthly
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	NERSC
Improvement	Building optimal training and testing datasets suitable for assessing/predicting HABs probability by merging multi-platform data.
External Link/Access channel	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10671482

3.10. Inland-marine water connectivity

Table 17.- Riverine inherent optical properties data product sheet

INLAND-MARINE WATER CONNECTIVITY	
Data product information	
Full Name	Riverine Inherent Optical Properties
Description	Bulk Inherent Optical Properties (IOPs): absorption (a ; m^{-1}), backscattering (bb ; m^{-1}) and water turbidity (FNU) at Pontelagoscuro (from S2-MSI) and Ca'Zuliani (from S2-MSI) to be compared with IOPs off the river mouth from S2-MSI and S3-OLCI
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	Po River Delta
Spatial coverage	Fixed points at three locations: Pontelagoscuro [44.88°, 11.61°]; Cavanella [45.03°, 12.16°], PILA [44.96°, 12.49°]
Time Span	From 01/01/2020 to 31/12/2020
Spatial resolution	Fixed points at three locations
Temporal resolution	Weekly
Variables	Optics
Feature type	Point
Update frequency / Latency	Yearly
Format	CSV
Provider	CNR
Improvement	Exploitation of high-spatial resolution missions/sensors synergy, between Sentinel-2 MSI and Sentinel-3 OLCI products in order to assess bio-optical connectivity between riverine and marine waters off the Po River Mouth
External Link/Access channel	N/A

3.11. Sea level and currents

Table 18.- Sea level and currents data product sheet

SEA LEVEL AND CURRENTS	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	Sea level and currents and water's properties
Description	Combination of gliders and Argo floats for assessing the water's properties induced by mesoscale features, use of HFR and drifters for surface currents and SWOT wide-swath altimetry to resolve sea level and currents.
Source	In-situ observations Satellite High-frequency radars
Area or Geographical coverage	Atlantic; NW European Shelf; Atlantic; Iberia-Biscay-Ireland; Arctic Ocean
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [60° to 78°] · Lon [-30.5° to 42°]
Time Span	From 01/09/2023 to 30/11/2023
Spatial resolution	2km for swath
Temporal resolution	Irregular
Variables	Sea surface height; Velocity; Temperature; Salinity
Feature type	Swath; Point; Trajectory
Update frequency / Latency	None
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	NERSC
Improvement	Colocation of wide-swath altimetry data and in-situ as a function of the ocean eddy population.
External Link/Access channel	https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/data/products/sea-surface-height-products/global/swot-l3-ocean-products.html https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/fr/data/products/sea-surface-height-products/global/experimental-multimission-gridded-l4-sea-level-heights-and-velocities-with-swot.html https://erddap.ifremer.fr/erddap/tabledap/ArgoFloats.html https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/INSITU_GLO_PHY_UV_DIS_CRETE_MY_013_044/description

3.12. FRM for ocean color and sea surface temperature radiometer observations

3.12.1. In-situ radiometric measurements for ocean color in riverine water

Table 19.-In-situ radiometry for ocean colour validation data product sheet

3.12.2. Fiducial reference sea surface temperature observations

Table 20.- Fiducial reference SST observations data product sheet

FRM FOR SST RADIOMETER OBS	
Data product information	
Full Name	Fiducial reference SST observations
Description	FRM Sea surface temperature observations using Infrared Scanning Autonomous Radiometer (ISAR) measurements from ships of opportunity
Source	In-situ observations
Area or Geographical coverage	North Sea
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Iceland, Faroe Islands, Denmark, and potentially Baltic/Mediterranean Sea
Time Span	From 11/07/2016 to 05/10/2024
Spatial resolution	Single point (fix point)
Temporal resolution	Instantaneous; Irregular
Variables	Temperature
Feature type	Timeseries; Point
Update frequency / Latency	Yearly 3 Minutes
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	DMI
Improvement	Use of coastal FRMs to validate spaceborne optical and thermal missions.
External Link/Access channel	N/A

3.13. Beach morphodynamic processes

3.13.1. Beach-imaging AI-derived shorelines

Table 21.- Beach-imaging AI-derived shorelines data product sheet

SHORELINES	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	Shoreline position
Description	Shoreline positions derived from land-based remote sensing observing platforms like beach video-monitoring systems and CoastSnap stations using automated AI-based workflows.
Source	Beach monitoring imagery
Area or Geographical coverage	Balearic Islands; Iberian Peninsula
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [36° to 43.80°] · Lon [-9.50° to 4.35°]
Time Span	From 2011 to 2024
Spatial resolution	1-3 m
Temporal resolution	Irregular
Variables	X, Y, Z
Feature type	Multi Point
Update frequency	Yearly
Format	.shp
Provider	SOCIB; +ATLANTIC
Improvement	Optimization of beach imaging platforms through novel development and implementation of advanced methods for image segmentation and shoreline extraction.
External Link	Link to Section 4.1.1 of “FOCCUS T2.3.1 Report”

3.13.2. Satellite derived shorelines

Table 22.- Satellite derived shorelines (SDS) data product sheet

SHORELINES	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	Shoreline position
Description	Shoreline positions derived from multispectral satellites, namely Sentinel-2 and PlanetScope, using automated AI-based workflows.
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	Balearic Islands; Iberian Peninsula; Black Sea
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [36° to 43.80°] · Lon [-9.50° to 4.35°]; Lat [43.74° to 45.15°] · Lon [28.55° to 29.80°]
Time Span	From 2015 to 2024
Spatial resolution	4-10 m
Temporal resolution	Irregular
Variables	X,Y
Feature type	MultiPoint
Update frequency	Yearly
Format	.shp
Provider	SOCIB; +ATLANTIC
Improvement	Extended spatiotemporal coverage of shoreline positions through the novel development and implementation of advanced methods for image segmentation and shoreline extraction from Sentinel-2 and PlanetScope.
External Link	Link to Section 4.1.2 of "FOCCUS_T2.3.1_Report"

3.13.3. Beach-imaging derived beach wracks

Table 23.- Beach-imaging derived beach wracks data product sheet

Beach wracks

DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION

Full Name	Beach seagrass wracks position
Description	Approximate beach seagrass wracks location across time and space derived from beach video-monitoring systems imagery.
Source	Beach monitoring imagery
Area or Geographical coverage	Balearic Islands
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [39.25° to 40.10°] · Lon [2.30° to 4.35°]
Time Span	From 2011 to 2024
Spatial resolution	5 m x 5 m
Temporal resolution	Irregular
Variables	X,Y
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency	Yearly
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	SOCIB
Improvement	Automated identification and delineation of Beach Wracks using segmentation (AI), object recognition (AI), and photogrammetry-based data georeferencing.
External Link	Link to Section 4.2 of “FOCCUS_T2.3.1_Report”

3.13.4. Satellite-derived bathymetry

Table 24.- Satellite-derived bathymetry data product sheet

Shallow water bathymetry	
DATA PRODUCT INFORMATION	
Full Name	Satellite-derived bathymetry (SDB)
Description	Shallow water bathymetry (depth from 0 - 15 m) derived from Sentinel-2 and PlanetScope multispectral sensors.
Source	Satellite
Area or Geographical coverage	Balearic Islands; Iberian Peninsula; Black Sea
Spatial coverage	Coastal area · Lat [36° to 43.80°] · Lon [-9.50° to 4.35°]; Lat [43.74° to 45.15°] · Lon [28.55° to 29.80°]
Time Span	From 2015 to 2024
Spatial resolution	4 m to 10 m
Temporal resolution	Irregular
Variables	X, Y, Z
Feature type	Grid
Update frequency	Bi-monthly
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	+ATLANTIC; MHD
Improvement	High spatial coverage and temporal resolution monitoring of shallow water bathymetry via hybrid approaches using statistical, physics-based and AI methods.
External Link	Link to Section 4.3 of “FOCCUS_T2.3.1_Report”

3.14. Coastal data

The **coastal data inventory** will be included in deliverable **D2.3** by June 2025. The report will include the main coastal datasets from networks, Research Infrastructures (RIs), programmes or projects in the most relevant and simple way to provide a good overview of the coastal data identified thanks to the FOCCUS project.

The data product sheet below provides a summary of the data products to be generated.

Table 25.- In-situ coastal data product sheet

COASTAL DATA	
Data product information	
Full Name	Highlighting of European in situ coastal data
Description	Major datasets (form networks, RI, projects or programmes) of coastal measurements tagged (metadata) as such in CMEMS and other EU data integrators
Source	In-situ observations
Area or Geographical coverage	Europe; Global Ocean
Spatial coverage	Lat [30° to 70°] · Lon [-16° to 42°]
Time Span	all possible time series (when data available)
Spatial resolution	at measurement point
Temporal resolution	Irregular
Variables	Sea surface height; Temperature; Salinity; Wave; current
Feature type	Point
Update frequency / Latency	Daily
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	Ifremer
Improvement	Identification of coastal observation in CMEMS and EU data integrators
External Link/Access channel	N/A

3.15. River data

The **river data inventory** is expected to be included in deliverable **D2.3** by June 2025. The inventory will include a list of major rivers based on geographical distribution (sea basin, e.g. Atlantic Ocean, Baltic Sea, Black Sea, and Mediterranean Sea), data availability, and water discharge levels, also considering the platform name, the agency that provides the data and URL if available, the coordinates of the platform (in terms of latitude and longitude), the most recent data and the variable (e.g. river flow rate, total suspended matter outflow, nutrients - nitrogen and phosphorous -, sediments).

The data product sheet below provides a summary of the data products to be generated and distributed by EMODnet.

Table 26.- River data product sheet

RIVER DATA	
Data product information	
Full Name	River near time data
Description	This product includes near-real time river data for the most coastal station free from tidal influence for each river when available.
Source	In-situ observations
Area or Geographical coverage	Atlantic: Iberia-Biscay-Ireland, Mediterranean Sea, Baltic Sea, Black Sea; Atlantic: NW European Shelf; Atlantic: Iberia-Biscay-Ireland
Spatial coverage	Lat [-31.651° to 70.140°] · Lon [-137.977° to 28.377°]
Time Span	From 01/01/2012 to today
Spatial resolution	Point
Temporal resolution	DailyHourly
Variables	River runoff; Temperature; River Water Height
Feature type	Point
Update frequency / Latency	Daily
Format	NetCDF-4
Provider	+ATLANTIC
External Link/Access channel	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en

4. Data products description

This section provides **detailed descriptions** of the data products listed in [Table 1](#), including a brief **overview, key variables, methodologies** and potential **use cases** for the data. It also includes **specific metadata** for each data product. The metadata described herein represents the current state of documentation for these data products. As development progresses, we anticipate refinements and additions to the metadata to ensure alignment with evolving standards, vocabularies and best practices. The final, validated metadata will be available in Deliverable 3.2

This information provides users with a comprehensive understanding of the data products and their applications.

4.1. Sea level

SEA LEVEL - Remote Sensing		
	<p>OVERVIEW: Sea Surface Height for coastal applications obtained from Level-3 data.</p> <p>This dataset includes observations from Sentinel-6A and SWOT missions. The data corresponds to Level-3 data processing, including the latest corrections applied to the Sea Surface Height observations obtained from satellite altimetry (instrumental and geophysical).</p> <p>The datasets available span the so-called European region: 20° to 66° N, -30° E to 42° E.</p>	
MAIN VARIABLES		
Name	Units (SI)	Description
LATITUDE	degrees_north	Latitude of measurements
LONGITUDE	degrees_east	Longitude of measurements
SEA SURFACE HEIGHT	m	Sea surface height above a reference datum
MEAN SEA SURFACE	m	Mean of the sea surface height relative to ellipsoid over a long time-series.
TIME	days since 1950- 01-01T00:00:00Z	Time of measurement
CYCLE	1	Cycle the measurement belongs to
TRACK	1	Track in cycle the measurement belongs to
QUALITY FLAG	1	Data quality flag.
SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY		
<p>Algorithm description:</p>	<p>Sea Level observations include several standard altimetric corrections (Pujol et al., 2023). Moreover, coastal observations benefit from the latest developments in altimetric standards. Among several correction terms, recently updated standards include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic Atmospheric Correction (DAC): TUGO model • Ocean Tides: FES 2022 • Internal Tides (M2, K1, S2, O1): HRET v8.1 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mean Sea Surface (MSS): Composite (SCRIPPS22,CNES/CLS22,DTU21) <p>In addition to the above listed novel corrections, common to S6 and SWOT datasets, specific corrections are needed for the measurements made by KaRIn swath interferometer embarked on SWOT.</p> <p>A SWOT-specific correction is also applied to KaRIn data, the Cross-calibration (XCAL). This correction is characteristic for the interferometric technique and accounts for the platform induced errors that influence the SSH measurements. The reference for the XCAL algorithm is Dibarboure et al., June 2022, SWOT Science Team meeting, SWOT simulated Level-2 and Level-3 data-driven calibration and Dibarboure et al., 2022.</p> <p>The correction applied on the 250x250m product is an interpolation of the solution computed using 2x2km data.</p> <p>Quality flags can be found in both Sentinel 6A and SWOT datasets, but differ in nature. Whereas for S6A the quality flag is boolean (0,1) indicating if the data are valid or not, SWOT data flags are more complex in nature;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flag #102: No SSHa values available. • Flag #101: Pixels over land. • Flag #100: Edges of swath. Only values between 10 to 60 km to the nadir are considered valid data. • Flag #70: Pixels impacted by spacecraft events. • Flag #50: Abnormally high SSHa values. • Flag #30: SSHa pixels from expected statistical distribution. • Flag #20: Suspected sea-ice pixels. • Flag #10: Suspected coastal pixels. • Flag #5: SSHa pixels from local distribution. • Flag #0: Valid data. <p>Details about each flag are available in Dibarboure et al (2024). For most studies, the recommendation is to keep a flag #0.</p>
<p>Limitations:</p>	<p>Geophysical and instrumental corrections are applied to obtain the Sea Surface Height measurements. Imperfect corrections could lead to errors in the measurements. Although this is very limited, data coming from new technology as KaRIn should be interpreted with care.</p> <p>SWOT is not an operational mission and data availability is dependent on the mission's operations. Data flow interruptions could occur although they are rare.</p>
<p>METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)</p>	
<p>format_version</p>	<p>"v0.1"</p>

title	“ Along Track L3 Sea Surface Heights”
summary	Instantaneous Level-3 Sea Surface Height Anomalies over the European Seas from Sentinel-3 and SWOT missions.
source_platform_category_code	“Satellite observations”
platform	“Sentinel-3A/B ; SWOT”
platform_type	“Satellite altimeter”
platform_vocabulary	“S3; SWOT”
instrument	Sentinel-3: Dual frequency SRAL Radar altimeter. SWOT: KaRIn Ka band radar interferometer, POS-5 Radar Altimeter
instrument_vocabulary	“S3, SWOT, KaRIn”
institution	“CLS”
institution_edmo_code	“5934”
references	S3: https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00147 SWOT: https://doi.org/10.24400/527896/A01-2023.017
product_version	“1.0”
comment	Sea Surface Height measured by altimeters referenced to the [1993, 2012] period. Detailed information regarding the data set's processing can be found in the product's handbook.
area	European Seas
cdm_data_type	swath
geospatial_lat_min	20.0° N
geospatial_lat_max	66.14942° N
geospatial_lon_min	30° W
geospatial_lon_max	42° E
geospatial_vertical_min	0
geospatial_vertical_max	0
geospatial_vertical_positive	down
geospatial_vertical_resolution	point
grid_resolution	“S3: 7km; SWOT: 2km”
update_interval	“void”
processing_level	“L3”
creator_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5673-8192
creator_url	“ https://www.cls.fr ”
contributor_name	0000-0001-5673-8192, 0000-0002-6701-6168
method	“in-situ measurements, quality control, gridding, and interpolation”
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	“ overgara@groupcls.com ”
technical_support_contact	“ aviso@altimetry.fr ”; “ servicedesk.cmems@mercator-ocean.eu ”
USE CASES	
Overview	Accurate sea level measurements in the coastal area provide the basis for analysing sea level trends and impacts in the coastal area. Furthermore, multi-year data allows for evaluating interannual variability in a context of climate change. SWOT

	<p>observations, with unprecedented spatial resolution, will allow to address the fine-scale coastal dynamics, as a complement of in situ data.</p> <p>Finally, L3 high resolution data can be used to constrain coastal OGCM simulations.</p>
<p>Benefits for user/model/application</p>	<p>FOCCUS User. The scientific community can use this data for ocean modelling, data assimilation, and studying coastal dynamics.</p> <p>FOCCUS Model. Sea level is a key variable in forcing coastal simulations. It can also be assimilated in forecast models. Overall, including quality controlled sea level observations in the modelling strategy will improve its skill. The experiments will be based on the WMOP model applied to the Mediterranean Sea.</p> <p>FOCCUS Application. This application indirectly addresses several key objectives of FOCCUS ESCs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ESC2 - Support to multi-use of coastal and off-shore operations: coastal circulation model forcing and characterization of circulation variability at different spatio-temporal scales. ● ESC3 - Storm surges and coastal flooding : model forcing and validation. Identification and characterization of extreme events. ● ESC3 - Combating degradation of ecosystems: model forcing and sea level trends monitoring.

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HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?

The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.

4.2. Sea surface temperature (SST)

SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE

OVERVIEW: High-resolution sea surface temperature for coastal applications obtained from multi-sensor merging.

This product provides daily merged multi-sensor maps of Sea Surface Temperature (SST), also known as super-collated Level-3S (L3S) maps, over the northern Adriatic Sea at a nominal spatial resolution of approximately 1 km. Representing mean conditions at midnight (00:00 UTC), the temperature provided is the foundation SST, meaning it is unaffected by diurnal warming (Minnett et al., 2019). The data is generated by merging information from various satellite infrared sensors, including the Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer (SLSTR) instruments onboard the Sentinel-3A and Sentinel-3B satellites, as well as the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) sensor onboard the Metop-B and Metop-C satellites, and the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer (VIIRS) onboard the Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership (SNPP) and NOAA-20 satellites (Buongiorno Nardelli et al., 2013).

To improve coastal applications, this product applies a relaxation of SST Quality Level (QL) flags on L2 data before ingestion into the super-collating processing chain. This adjustment allows for the

	inclusion of SST data that may have been erroneously identified as clouds, addressing potential cloud mask failures in areas with intense cold coastal currents, upwellings, or sharp SST gradients.	
MAIN VARIABLES		
Name	Units (SI)	Description
lat	degrees_north	latitude of measurements
lon	degrees_east	longitude of measurements
time	seconds since 1981-01-01 00:00:00Z	reference time of SST field
adjusted_sea_surface_temperature	kelvin	sea surface temperature adjusted to the reference
SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY		
Algorithm description:	<p>Daily, gridded, merged multi-sensor (L3S) SST data are obtained by collating different upstream level-2 (L2) observations, which e.g. include those acquired from very accurate infrared radiometers such as SLSTR, VIIRS and AVHRR. However, SST values from different sensors can vary significantly due to differences in sensor characteristics—such as band configuration, spectral resolution, and scanning/viewing geometry— and due to the specific atmospheric correction algorithms applied. To address these discrepancies, a bias adjustment procedure is applied to each L2 dataset during merging. This algorithm accounts for data continuity within the L3S image by estimating and locally removing (within a 50 km radius) any bias between each input image and an initial guess field. The final dataset then prioritises ‘best’ data based on a measure of data density, with sparse or scattered data given lower preference. In the current operational production of this product, which is distributed via the Copernicus Marine Service, only data with the highest quality flags are retained. While this approach ensures the selection of the best-quality SST measurements, it can lead to the exclusion of valid data, particularly in coastal areas or regions with strong temperature gradients, where data may be mistakenly flagged as low quality. To enhance coastal monitoring, this product introduces a relaxation of SST Quality Level (QL) flags on Level-2 data before it enters the multi-sensor merging procedure. This adjustment helps incorporate SST data that may have been incorrectly flagged as clouds, addressing potential cloud masking issues in regions with strong coastal currents, upwellings, or intense SST gradients.</p>	
Limitations:	<p>This product is derived from the Copernicus Marine Service Ultra-High Resolution (UHR) Mediterranean SST product (https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00172), ensuring that technical risks related to data production and system functionality are minimal. For coastal applications, however, certain limitations remain. First, the spatial resolution, while high, cannot reach sub-kilometric scales, which may restrict the detection of finer coastal dynamics. Additionally, some valid SST measurements may still be flagged as</p>	

	low quality due to upstream processing criteria, potentially leading to gaps in data coverage in regions with complex temperature patterns.
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES	
format_version	"v0.1"
convention	"CF-1.4"
netcdf_version	"NetCDF 4"
title	"High-Resolution L3S Sea Surface Temperature"
summary	"Regional, daily, merged high-resolution (~1 km) multi-sensor (level-3S, L3S) SST product (from Sentinel-3, MetOp, SNPP, NOAA-20) over specific coastal regions".
source_platform_category_code	"satellite"
platform	"Sentinel-3A, Sentinel-3B, SUOMI-NPP, MetOp-B (NOAA-20, MetOp-C, available from 2023)"
platform_type	"low earth orbit satellite"
platform_vocabulary	"CEOS"
instrument	"SLSTR; VIIRS; AVHRR"
instrument_vocabulary	"CEOS"
institution	"CNR-ISMAR"
institution_edmo_code	"227"
references	"Buongiorno Nardelli, B., Tronconi, C., Pisano, A., Santoleri, R. (2013). High and Ultra-High resolution processing of satellite Sea Surface Temperature data over Southern European Seas in the framework of MyOcean project. Remote Sensing of Environment, 129, 1-16"
product_version	"1.0"
comment	"First version of the high-resolution regional SST product"
area	"Northern Adriatic Sea"
cdm_data_type	"grid"
geospatial_lat_min	43.47°
geospatial_lat_max	44.30°
geospatial_lon_min	12.22°
geospatial_lon_max	13.05°
geospatial_vertical_min	0
geospatial_vertical_max	0
geospatial_vertical_positive	0
geospatial_vertical_resolution	0
grid_resolution	0.01° x 0.01°
update_interval	irregular
processing_level	L3
creator_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9465-8457 ;

	https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7744-6048 ; https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8767-4379 ;
creator_url	https://www.ismar.cnr.it/
contributor_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9465-8457 ; https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7744-6048 ; https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8767-4379 ;
method	“satellite data processing”
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	gSDK@artov.ismar.cnr.it
technical_support_contact	gSDK@artov.ismar.cnr.it
USE CASES	
Overview	<p>Accurate mapping of SST in coastal areas is crucial for monitoring local trends, assessing extreme events such as marine heatwaves, and evaluating impacts on local ecosystems. The high spatial resolution of this dataset enables monitoring at meso- to sub-mesoscale, allowing for detailed observation of oceanic dynamics such as fronts and small-scale upwellings. These processes are vital for the distribution of heat, nutrient transport, and ecosystem variability in both coastal and open ocean regions. Additionally, L3S sea surface temperatures can be used for data assimilation purposes.</p>
Benefits for user/model/application	<p>FOCCUS User. Users can benefit from accurate high-resolution SST data, characteristics that are essential for coastal applications. These data support a range of activities, from monitoring temperature fluctuations, detection of marine heatwaves and algal blooms to assessing fishery zones and coastal ecosystem health (Gobler 2020; Marullo et al. 2023; Li et al. 2024). With access to historical SST records available through the Copernicus Marine Service, users can track long-term temperature variability, estimate SST trends to evaluate the impacts of global warming (Pisano et al. 2020), and analyse the evolution of extreme events such as marine heatwaves (Juza et al., 2022, Martinez et al. 2023) and Mediterranean tropical-like cyclones (Avolio et al. 2024). Operational SST data enable timely decision-making and response, which is critical for managing marine resources, supporting sustainable aquaculture, and enhancing coastal resilience to climate impacts.</p> <p>FOCCUS Model. SST data serve valuable roles in both validation and assimilation processes. Assimilation of SST data in ocean and climate models can improve forecast accuracy and representation of ocean dynamics.</p> <p>FOCCUS Application. In addition to the above mentioned applications (see FOCCUS User and FOCCUS model), the L3S SST product could be used to validate and/or calibrate SST data acquired from ECOSTRESS, investigating potential retrieval of SST from hyper</p>

	spatial resolution satellite sensors (70 m) in transitional/estuarine waters (not committed in the project).
KEY REFERENCES	
<p>Avolio, E., Fanelli, C., Pisano, A., Miglietta, M. M. (2024). Unveiling the relationship between Mediterranean tropical-like cyclones and rising Sea Surface Temperature. <i>Geophysical Research Letters</i>, 51, e2024GL109921. https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL109921</p> <p>Buongiorno Nardelli, B., Tronconi, C., Pisano, A., and Santoleri R. (2013). High and Ultra-High resolution processing of satellite Sea Surface Temperature data over Southern European Seas in the framework of MyOcean project. <i>Remote Sensing of Environment</i>, Vol. 129, pg. 1-16. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.10.012</p> <p>Gobler, C. J. (2020). Climate change and harmful algal blooms: insights and perspective. <i>Harmful algae</i>, 91, 101731.</p> <p>Juza, M., Fernández-Mora, À., & Tintoré, J. (2022). Sub-Regional Marine Heat Waves in the Mediterranean Sea From Observations: Long-Term Surface Changes, Sub-Surface and Coastal Responses. In <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i> (Vol. 9). https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fmars.2022.785771</p> <p>Li, M., Organelli, E., Serva, F., Bellacicco, M., Landolfi, A., Pisano, A., Marullo, S., Shen, F., Mignot, A., van Gennip, S., Santoleri, R. (2024). Phytoplankton spring bloom inhibited by marine heatwaves in the North-Western Mediterranean Sea. <i>Geophysical Research Letters</i>, 51, e2024GL109141. https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL109141</p> <p>Marullo, S., Serva, F., Iacono, R., Napolitano, E., di Sarra, A., Meloni, D., Monteleone, F., Sferlazzo, D., De Silvestri, L., De Toma, V., Pisano, A., Bellacicco, M., Landolfi, A., Organelli, E., Yang, C., Santoleri, R. (2023). Record-breaking persistence of the 2022/23 marine heatwave in the Mediterranean Sea. <i>Environmental Research Letters</i>, 18(11), 114041. https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ad02ae</p> <p>Martínez, J., Leonelli, F. E., García-Ladona, E., Garrabou, J., Kersting, D. K., Bensoussan, N., Pisano, A. (2023). Evolution of Marine Heatwaves in warming seas: the Mediterranean Sea study-case. <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i>, 10, 1193164. https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2023.1193164</p> <p>Minnett, P. J., Alvera-Azcárate, A., Chin, T. M., Corlett, G. K., Gentemann, C. L., Karagali, I., Li, X., Marsouin, A., Marullo, S., Maturi, E., Santoleri, R., Saux Picart, S., Steele, M., Vazquez-Cuervo, J. (2019). Half a century of satellite remote sensing of sea-surface temperature. <i>Remote Sensing of Environment</i>, 233, 111366.</p> <p>Pisano, A.; Marullo, S.; Artale, V.; Falcini, F.; Yang, C.; Leonelli, F.E.; Santoleri, R.; Buongiorno Nardelli, B. New Evidence of Mediterranean Climate Change and Variability from Sea Surface Temperature Observations. <i>Remote Sens.</i> 2020, 12, 132. doi: https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12010132</p>	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.	

4.3. Sea ice changes

SEA ICE

OVERVIEW: High-resolution land-fast sea ice detection in coastal areas is based on roughness and drift obtained from Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images. This will improve the automated sea ice type classification currently available in CMEMS. The SAR data used are Sentinel-1 dual-polarised (HH/HV polarisation combination) recorded in Extra wide swath mode with a swath width of 410 km and a spatial resolution of 93x87 m (pixel spacing of 40x40m). Landfast ice is detected where the ice drift algorithm works correctly and the ice drift speed is zero.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description (long_name)
landfast_ice		Land fast ice
confidence	%	Confidence level

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	<p>In the pre-processing, the Sentinel-1 backscatter data are calibrated into sigma-nought values for each pixel and subsampled to 80x80 m pixel size to reduce speckle noise. Next, the sea ice drift (SID) is estimated from consecutive S1 SAR images using the combined feature tracking and pattern matching algorithm (Korosov et al., 2018).</p> <p>An updated version of the SID algorithm will be used to process S1 data. First, virtual ice-drifting buoys will be initialised in the region of interest (ROI) on a regular grid. Then, for each new coming S1 image, the following steps are performed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detect buoys overlapped with the S1 image • Compute descriptors using the ORB method for each buoy • Run matching with previously detected buoys (if any) <p>As a result, we will have virtual buoys trajectories for the entire ROI with one-pass processing of each S1 image. SID is estimated successfully only in regions with a consistent pattern of SAR backscatter, i.e., in areas covered by pack ice or land-fast sea ice. In the marginal ice zone (MIZ) or in open water, ice drift cannot be estimated due to rapid changes in SAR image patterns. Thus, the first-order classification into ice/no ice is achieved by filtering the valid SID observations.</p> <p>Next, land-fast ice is detected on SID products as ice with nearly zero drift.</p>
Limitations:	Availability of S1 data limits the extent of the product.

METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)

format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Land-fast ice extent"
summary	"Land-fast ice extent is derived from sequences of SAR images using sea ice drift estimates."
source_platform_category_code	"satellite"

platform	"Sentinel-1"
platform_type	"polar Earth orbit satellite"
platform_vocabulary	GCMD
instrument	C-SAR
instrument_vocabulary	GCMD
institution	"Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center"
institution_edmo_code	"1413"
references	"Korosov, A.A.; Rampal, P. A Combination of Feature Tracking and Pattern Matching with Optimal Parameterization for Sea Ice Drift Retrieval from SAR Data. Remote Sens. 2017, 9, 258. https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9030258 "
product_version	"1.0"
comment	"First version of the fast ice extent product"
cdm_data_type	"grid"
area	"Greenland coast and Svalbard"
geospatial_lat_min	57
geospatial_lat_max	80
geospatial_lon_min	-42
geospatial_lon_max	40
geospatial_vertical_min	0
geospatial_vertical_max	0
geospatial_vertical_resolution	0
update_interval	"irregular"
processing_level	"L2"
creator_url	" https://nersc.no "
contributor_name	"0000-0002-3601-1161"
contributor_url	" https://nersc.no "
contributor_email	"post@nersc.no"
method	"sea ice drift"
track_id	"NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Science Keywords"
USE CASES	
Overview	Detected land fast ice extent allows more accurate validation of coupled ocean / sea ice models in the coastal area.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User: MET.NO, SHOM, MOi FOCCUS Model: TOPAZ, NORKYST FOCCUS Application: ESC1 - Management and protection of coastal area
KEY REFERENCES	
Korosov, A.A.; Rampal, P. A Combination of Feature Tracking and Pattern Matching with Optimal Parameterization for Sea Ice Drift Retrieval from SAR Data. Remote Sens. 2017, 9, 258. https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9030258	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.	

4.4. High-resolution total surface currents

HIGH-RESOLUTION TOTAL SURFACE CURRENTS

OVERVIEW: A high-resolution total ocean surface current radial velocity product retrieved from Doppler Centroid Anomaly acquisitions obtained by the Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR). Each product covers a swath of 250 km with 1x1 km pixel size. The product covers the Norwegian Coastal zone reaching up to 300 km offshore.

The product is based on the operational Sentinel-1 Level 2 Ocean Radial Velocity products acquired in the Interferometric Wide (IW) mode VV polarisation processed with two-step algorithm: (1) Re-calibration of the satellite pointing errors due to antenna and platform attitude, (2) Removal of the sea-state-induced signal using an empirical geophysical model function.

The first step is implemented based on the RVL calibration processor which utilises a combination of auxiliary telemetry from a gyroscope onboard Sentinel-1 and data-driven calibration based on the acquisitions over the land within the same satellite datatake. The second step is implemented based on the CDOP3SiX algorithm which uses information about wind field, wind sea, and swell, to estimate and remove sea state contribution to the observed signal. The auxiliary model information is collocated from the operational ECMWF model (wind field, provided in S1 L2 product) and Arctic Ocean Wave Analysis and Forecast system (wind sea and swell, produced by MET Norway, distributed via CMEMS).

The final products are organised as a single file per satellite acquisition covering an area of 250 x 200 km. Each file contains geospatial grids and ocean surface current radial velocity field and radial direction field.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description (long_name)
lat	degrees north	Latitude
lon	degrees east	Longitude
doppler_centroid_anomaly	Hz	Geophysical Doppler shift
doppler_centroid_std	hz	Estimated doppler centroid frequency standard deviation
quality_level		confidence on Estimated doppler centroid frequency
land_area_fraction	1	fraction of land coverage within a cell
radial_direction	degrees	Radial direction of the SAR antenna (clockwise from North)
wave_bias	Hz	Estimated wave bias
osc_rvl	m/s	Total Ocean Surface Current Radial Velocity

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	The Sentinel-1 Ocean Surface Current Radial Velocity product is being developed for the FOCCUS project. The product contains information required for retrieval of the ocean surface current radial (line-of-sight) velocity from the Doppler shift observations acquired by the Sentinel-1 A/B Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) in the Interferometric Wide (IW) mode. The geophysical Doppler shift observations provided in the product were derived using advanced calibration of the non-geophysical contributions to the Sentinel-1 Doppler shift data previously detected in standard products. The geophysical Doppler shift over the ocean contains information about total surface motion induced by the sea state and the ocean surface currents, the product includes estimates of the sea state bias from the CDOP3SiX Geophysical Model Function (GMF) based on the collocated wind field at 10 m height from the ECMWF model and region-specific wave model. The product is continuously evaluated versus independent observations and found consistent with the daily gridded geostrophic velocity fields from the altimetry and satellite-derived Sea Surface temperature fields, and ocean surface drifter observations.
Limitations:	Reliability on the auxiliary model fields can lead to errors propagating from inaccurate forecasts to the retrieval algorithm
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
format_version	"v0.1"
Conventions	"Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7, Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3"
netcdf_version	"4.1.3"
netcdf_format	"netcdf4 classic"
title	"High-Resolution Total Surface Currents"
summary	"High-resolution ocean surface current velocity product derived from Sentinel-1 SAR data. Covers 250 km swath with 1 km pixel size along the Norwegian coast. Uses a two-step algorithm: recalibration of satellite pointing errors and removal of sea-state signal. Final products are geospatial grids with velocity and direction fields."
project	13800
source_platform_category_code	"Satellite"
phase	"operational"
platform	"Sentinel-1 A"
platform_type	"low earth orbit satellite"
platform_vocabulary	"CEOS"
instrument	"C-Band SAR"
instrument_vocabulary	"CEOS"
band	"C"
polarisation	"VV"
radar_wavenumber	"113.28034"
institution	"Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center"

institution_edmo_code	"3410"
references	"Moiseev, A., Johnsen, H., Johannessen, J. A., Collard, F., & Guitton, G. (2020). On removal of sea state contribution to Sentinel-1 Doppler shift for retrieving Reliable Ocean surface current. Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans, 125, e2020JC016288. https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JC016288 "
product_version	"1.0"
version_date	"2024-09-17T00:30:00Z"
keywords	"Earth Science > Oceans > Ocean Circulation > Ocean Currents"
keywords_vocabulary	"NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Science Keywords"
comment	—
time_coverage_start	"2024-09-17T00:30:00Z"
time_coverage_end	"2024-09-17T00:30:00Z"
geospatial_lat_units	"degree_north"
geospatial_lon_units	"degree_east"
geospatial_vertical_units	"metres above mean sea level"
grid_resolution	"1 km"
reference_system	"EPSG:4806"
citation	"The data were collected and made freely available through the FOCCUS project (EU GA.No. 101133911) and the national programs that contribute to it"
publisher_url	https://zenodo.org/
publisher_institution	ZENODO
licence	"This data product is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License"
acknowledgement	"FOCCUS, Funded by the European Union, Grant Agreement No. 101133911 "
date_created	"2024-09-16T00:30:00Z"
history	"2024-09-16T00:30:00Z data created"
processing_level	"L2"
creator_name	0000-0002-6475-5088
creator_url	" https://nersc.no "
contributor_name	0000-0002-6475-5088
contributor_url	" https://nersc.no "
contributor_email	post@nersc.no
method	"Attitude and residual bias correction / CDOP3SiX Geophysical Model Function"
track_id	"10.1038/s41597-023-02210-2"
scientific_support_contact	post@nersc.no
USE CASES	
Overview	The product can be used to monitor ocean surface currents with a kilometre resolution. Thanks to high spatial resolution these direct observations of the ocean surface current provide an opportunity for studying ocean dynamics processes in the coastal areas such as eddies and filaments. It also provides a valuable independent dataset to validate coastal models.

Benefits for user/model/application	<p>FOCCUS User. The scientific community (ocean modelling and data assimilation) can use the product for studying mesoscale ocean circulation processes in the coastal areas and assimilating it in the relevant model system or/and independent validation. The product can be also utilised for developing of multisensory ocean current products, e.g., based on combination of the satellite altimetry, HF radars, and SAR in the european seas</p> <p>FOCCUS Model. The product will be used by the coastal modelling community for validation of high resolution Norkyst (developed by MET Norway) ocean forecasting systems in the Norwegian Coastal Zone.]</p> <p>FOCCUS Application. Although the product is intended to be used by the intermediate users in the ocean modelling community in cal indirectly lead to the benefits regarding following FOCCUS applications:</p> <p>ESC1 - Pollution hazard - the product can enhance the ocean current forecasting and validation leading to better forecasting and response to the pollution hazards</p> <p>ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding - the use of the product by relevant intermediate users and improve our understanding and forecasting of extreme coastal events</p>
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KEY REFERENCES

Moiseev, A., Johnsen, H., Hansen, M. W., & Johannessen, J. A. (2020). Evaluation of radial ocean surface currents derived from Sentinel-1 IW Doppler shift using coastal radar and Lagrangian surface drifter observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 125, e2019JC015743. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JC015743>

Moiseev, A., Johannessen, J. A., & Johnsen, H. (2022). Towards retrieving reliable ocean surface currents in the coastal zone from the Sentinel-1 Doppler shift observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 127, e2021JC018201. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JC018201>

HOW TO USE AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?

The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.

4.5. Bio-geo-chemical (BGC) anomalies and trends

4.5.1 BGC anomalies and trends - CNR

BGC ANOMALIES AND TRENDS

OVERVIEW: Full spatial resolution Chlorophyll (Chl) and Total Suspended Matter (TSM) concentration satellite products for coastal applications.

This product provides weekly merged single sensor products of Chlorophyll and Total Suspended Matter concentration, as Level-3S (L3S) maps, over the North Adriatic Sea at a nominal spatial resolution of approximately 300 m. The product also provides weekly maps of both Chl and TSM concentration anomalies (Braga

	et al., 2022), evaluated over the 2016-2023 S3-OLCI time series, and the related statistical trends (Colella et al., 2016).	
MAIN VARIABLES		
Name	Units (SI)	Description
lat	degrees_north	latitude of measurements
lon	degrees_east	longitude of measurements
time	seconds since 2016-05-01 00:00:00Z	reference time of SST field
chlorophyll_concentration	mg m ⁻³	mass concentration of chlorophyll in seawater
total suspended matter	g m ⁻³	total suspended matter in seawater
SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY		
Algorithm description:	<p>Collection of the full time series (May 2016 – to present) of OLCI EO Level-2 full resolution (300 m) data from the EUMETSAT data centre. Level-2 products were then extracted and remapped over a regular equirectangular grid in the North Adriatic Sea. We applied the CMEMS operational algorithms for phytoplankton chlorophyll retrieval (Volpe et al., 2019), adapted to OLCI bands (the algorithm exploits the 555 nm band, while OLCI has the band centred over the 560 nm channel) and implemented on a daily basis. This algorithm treats open (Case I) and coastal (Case II) waters separately by applying and merging different algorithms. TSM derives from the neural network algorithm operationally implemented and distributed by EUMETSAT. The OLCI daily time series is then turned into a weekly time series by averaging on a pixel-by-pixel basis. For each pixel the average and standard deviation is computed from a data cube of 3 pixels x 3 pixels x 7 days. This averaging reduces the impact of possible noise, common at these small scales, and increases spatial coverage mined by lack of data mostly due to clouds. Finally, we consider the difference between the “present” weekly observations and the weekly climatology at the scale of the pixel. This difference needs to be judged against the climatology to obtain a relative, dimensionless value that represents the both Chl and TSM anomaly.</p> <p>Statistical trends of TSM and Chl are calculated by deseasonalizing the time series via the X-11 procedure, which decomposes the original time series (of both TSM and Chl) into three different components: the seasonal signal, the trend component, and an irregular component (Shiskin, 1978; Dagum, 1980). Then, the Mann-Kendal (MK) test and the Sens’s method (Mann, 1945; Kendall, 1948; Sen, 1968) will be applied to the deseasonalized time series of TSM and Chl to estimate the statistical trends.</p>	

Limitations:	Cloud cover, limited time series (from 2016) from climatological analysis
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Full-Resolution L3S Chlorophyll-a concentration" "Full-Resolution L3S Total Suspended Matter concentration"
summary	"Regional, weekly, single-sensor full-resolution (~300 m) (level-3S, L3S) Chl and TSM products (from Sentinel-3 over specific coastal regions, including weekly anomalies and trends".
source_platform_category_code	"satellite"
platform	"Sentinel-3A, Sentinel-3B"
platform_type	"low earth orbit satellite"
platform_vocabulary	"CEOS"
instrument	"OLCI"
instrument_vocabulary	"CEOS"
institution	"CNR-ISMAR"
institution_edmo_code	"227"
references	<p>"Volpe, G., Colella, S., Brando, V. E., Forneris, V., La Padula, F., Di Cicco, A., ... & Santoleri, R. (2019). Mediterranean ocean colour Level 3 operational multi-sensor processing. Ocean Science, 15(1), 127-146."</p> <p>"Colella, S., Falcini, F., Rinaldi, E., Sammartino, M., & Santoleri, R. (2016). Mediterranean ocean colour chlorophyll trends. PloS one, 11(6), e0155756."</p> <p>"Braga, F., Ciani, D., Colella, S., Organelli, E., Pitarch, J., Brando, V. E., ... & Falcini, F. (2022). COVID-19 lockdown effects on a coastal marine environment: Disentangling perception versus reality. Science of the Total Environment, 817, 153002."</p>
product_version	"1.0"
comment	"TSM products not available in the Copernicus Marine Service"; "First version of full-resolution regional OC anomalies and trends"
area	"North Adriatic Sea"
cdm_data_type	"grid"
time_coverage_resolution	P6D
time_coverage_duration	P1Y
geospatial_lat_min	43.47°
geospatial_lat_max	44.30°
geospatial_lon_min	12.22°
geospatial_lon_max	13.05°
geospatial_vertical_min	0
geospatial_vertical_max	0
geospatial_vertical_positive	0
geospatial_vertical_resolution	0

grid_resolution	0.003° x 0.003°
update_interval	irregular
processing_level	L3
creator_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7727-7353 https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3916-5393 https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8105-2491 https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7066-9258
creator_url	https://www.ismar.cnr.it/
contributor_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7727-7353 https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3916-5393 https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8105-2491 https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7066-9258
contributor_url	https://www.ismar.cnr.it/
contributor_email	federico.falcini@cnr.it
method	“satellite data processing”
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	gSDK@artov.ismar.cnr.it
technical_support_contact	gSDK@artov.ismar.cnr.it
USE CASES	
Overview	<p>This set of products will help to identify the major threats that act on coastal environments and, in particular, those connected to river inputs. To this purpose both statistical trends and anomalies of Ocean Colour (OC) products over coastal zones should highlight those nutrient inputs of terrestrial/anthropogenic origin that can lead to undesirable modifications of phytoplankton concentration (i.e., eutrophication). Chlorophyll is, indeed, a proxy of phytoplankton biomass and it is an efficient tool for recording and understanding the response of coastal ecosystems to human pressures and thus for detecting eutrophication; TSM, i.e., the concentration of organic and inorganic materials suspended in the water, is another proxy for water quality as different contaminants, including nutrients, trace metals, semi-volatile organic compounds, and numerous pesticides, can aggregate to these solids and brought in suspension. TSM can alter the state of the aquatic ecosystem and the use of freshwater resources; for instance, excessive suspended material might condition primary productivity.</p>
Benefits for user/model/application	<p>FOCCUS User. The set of products will be useful for HABs detection and/or assessment, and for water quality indicators. Potential users will be Aquaculture and Shell farmers, Coastal environmental agencies at national and regional level, which could potentially take proactive measures to protect marine ecosystems and human health or diagnose past events in the light of other environmental stressors.</p> <p>FOCCUS Model. Ocean Colour products in coastal environments represent valuable datasets for model validation and, in general, for</p>

the assessment of biogeochemical tracers dispersion due to coastal dynamics. Eventually these weekly products may serve for assimilation to improve predictability of water quality coastal patterns.

FOCCUS Application. The set of products will contribute to the following FOCCUS applications:

- ESC 1 - Applications to better manage and protect the coastal area: pollution hazard/risk mapping by assessing the cumulative impacts of land based pollution and sediment resuspension.
- ESC 2 - Applications to enhance blue economy: improving and integrating coastal observations and forecasting systems including biogeochemical processes.

KEY REFERENCES

Braga, F., Ciani, D., Colella, S., Organelli, E., Pitarch, J., Brando, V. E., ... & Falcini, F. (2022). COVID-19 lockdown effects on a coastal marine environment: Disentangling perception versus reality. *Science of the Total Environment*, 817, 153002.

Colella, S., Falcini, F., Rinaldi, E., Sammartino, M., & Santoleri, R. (2016). Mediterranean ocean colour chlorophyll trends. *PLoS one*, 11(6), e0155756.

Vona, I., Colella, S., Sammartino, M., Brando, V.E., Falcini, F. (2024) Direct Relationship Between River Discharge and Ocean Colour Trends of Chl and TSM in a semi-confined marine basin. *Scientific Reports* (under review)

HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?

The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025

4.5.2 BGC multisensor coastal product - BC

BGC ANOMALIES AND TRENDS

OVERVIEW: Daily multi-resolution, gapfree ocean colour products from a combination of high spatial resolution (Sentinel-2) and medium resolution data (Sentinel-3). This has been achieved by exploiting the synergy between these two missions, and provides high spatial resolution data at daily temporal resolution. The synergy analysis and gap-filling is done using DINEOF (Data Empirical Orthogonal Functions). The variables provided are turbidity -TUR-, suspended particulate matter concentration -SPM- and chlorophyll-a concentration -CHL-. The spatial resolution has been set to 100 m. Uptake and extension of work performed within Copernicus Marine TIER 3 project Multires conducted by University of Liège and RBINS.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description
turbidity	FNU	sea water turbidity

suspended_particle_matter_concentration	g m ⁻³	mass concentration of suspended particulate matter in sea water
chlorophyll_concentration	mg m ⁻³	mass concentration of chlorophyll in sea water

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description	<p>The process combines atmospheric correction and in water retrieval with a machine learning approach for best chlorophyll estimation. The ocean colour satellite processor used is based on the Copernicus Marine high-resolution processor (CMEMS HROC) using a multi-algorithm approach combining the best suited algorithm for different water types. This processor starts from L1C and L1 data for Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 respectively and combines atmospheric correction processing (C2RCC + ACOLITE DSF), IDEPIX pixel classification, ocean colour algorithm application and product quality control (i.e. glint flagging, bottom reflection flagging, etc.) to provide Analysis Ready Data Layers (ARDL) for the ocean colour variables: RRS, CHL, TUR and SPM. With the machine learning approach the input data is scaled using its mean and standard deviation, and the target CHL value is log transformed. Then DINEOF (Data Interpolating Empirical Orthogonal Functions, Beckers and Rixen (2003); Alvera-Azcárate et al. (2005)) is applied to reconstruct the missing data and enhance the resolution of the combined Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 datasets. An extension of the ML model to TUR and SPM is planned. Sentinel-2 data is used preferentially when both data is available before reconstruction, as it provides the highest spatial resolution.</p>
Limitations	<p>The availability of Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 data limits the product's reach. This approach has not yet been tested in all areas. The approach is available for CHL and will be transferred to TSM and TUR and needs further testing.</p>

METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)

title	"Multiresolution bio geochemical product"
summary	"The multiresolution product provides biogeochemical data via a synergy between Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 observations."
source_platform_category_code	"satellite"
phase	"demonstration"
platform	"Sentinel-2 A""Sentinel-2 B""Sentinel-3"
platform_type	"low earth orbit satellite"
platform_vocabulary	"CEOS"
instrument	"MSI,"OLCI"
institution	"Brockmann Consult GmbH"

institution_edmo_code	"_"
references	"Aida Alvera-Azcárate, Alexander Barth, Antoine Dille, Joppe Massant, Dimitry Van der Zande and Jean-Marie Beckers (224). Generation of super-resolution gap-free ocean colour satellite products using DINEOF. Submitted to Ocean Sciences."
product_version	"1.0"
version_date	"2025-02-28T00:30:00Z"
comment	"under development"
area	"North Sea", "Black Sea", "Iberian Coast"
cdm_data_type	"grid"
time_coverage_resolution	"P1D"
time_coverage_duration	"P1D"
geospatial_lat_min	"52°N"
geospatial_lat_max	"58°N"
geospatial_lon_min	"3°E"
geospatial_lon_max	"10°E"
geospatial_vertical_min	n/a
geospatial_vertical_max	n/a
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"integral up to visible depths"
grid_resolution	"100 m"
update_interval	"P1D"
processing_level	"L4D"
creator_name	"0000-0003-0831-6520"
creator_url	"https://www.brockmann-consult.de"
creator_email	"support@brockmann-consult.de"
creator_institution	"Brockmann Consult GmbH"
contributor_name	"0000-0002-2742-0721"
contributor_url	"https://odnature.naturalsciences.be/remsem/index"
contributor_email	"dvanderzande@naturalsciences.be"
method	"combination of data interpolation (DINEOF) and machine learning to generate gap free data"
track_id	unique id
keywords_vocabulary	"NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Science Keywords"
naming_authority	"org.esa-cci"
comment	—
keywords	ocean colour, water quality, reflectance, coastal waters, Copernicus Marine
netcdf_version_id	"4.6.1 of May 13 2018 11:35:43"
scientific_support_contact	"carole.lebreton@brockmann-consult.de"
technical_support_contact	"carole.lebreton@brockmann-consult.de"
key_variables	"turbidity ", "chlorophyll", "SPM"
source	"Sentinel-2 MSI L1C", "Sentinel-3 OLCI L1"
source_version	"1.0"
USE CASES	

Overview	The dataset can be used as boundary condition or for data assimilation in a model, providing daily gap-filled SPM, TUR, or CHL information that can be easily re-gridded to fit the model's grid.
Benefits for user/model/application	<p>FOCCUS User: HEREON</p> <p>FOCCUS Model: SCHISM-WWM-Xbeach</p> <p>FOCCUS Application: Applications to better manage and protect the coastal area</p>
KEY REFERENCES	
<p>Aida Alvera-Azcárate, Dimitry van der Zande, Joppe Massant, MultiRes Final report, Copernicus Marine Service Evolution 21036-COP-INNO SCI.</p> <p>Aida Alvera-Azcárate, Alexander Barth, Antoine Dille, Joppe Massant, Dimitry Van der Zande and Jean-Marie Beckers. Generation of super-resolution gap-free ocean colour satellite products using DINEOF. Submitted to Ocean Sciences.</p> <p>Alvera-Azcárate, A., Barth, A., Rixen, M., & Beckers, J. M. (2005). Reconstruction of incomplete oceanographic data sets using empirical orthogonal functions: application to the Adriatic Sea surface temperature. <i>Ocean Modelling</i>, 9(4), 325–346. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2004.08.001</p> <p>Beckers, J. M., & Rixen, M. (2003). EOF Calculations and Data Filling from Incomplete Oceanographic Datasets*. <i>Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology</i>, 20(12), 1839–1856. <a href="https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0426(2003)020<1839:ecadff>2.0.co;2">https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0426(2003)020<1839:ecadff>2.0.co;2</p> <p>Van Der Zande, D., Stelzer, K. Lebreton, C., Dille, A., Shevchuk, R., Santos, J., Böttcher, M., Vanhellemont, Q., and Sholze, J. Quality Information Document, OC-BC-RBINS Production Centre, 10 November 2022 (available at https://catalogue.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/QUID/CMEMS-HR-OC-QUID-009-201to212.pdf)</p> <p>Van der Zande, D., Vanhellemont, Q., Stelzer, K., Lebreton, C., Dille, A., dos Santos, J., Böttcher, M., Vansteenwegen, D., and Brockmann, C.: Improving operational ocean colour coverage using a merged atmospheric correction approach, in: <i>Remote Sensing of the Ocean, Sea Ice, Coastal Waters, and Large Water Regions</i>, edited by SPIE, vol. 12728, pp. 12–29, 2023.</p>	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025	

4.6. Seagrass and macroalgae

4.6.1 Emerged seagrass and macroalgae

EMERGED SEAGRASS AND MACROALGAE		
	<p>OVERVIEW: Annual maps of emerged aquatic vegetation on intertidal sand banks in the Wadden Sea of the German Bight. Vegetation percent cover is derived from temporal aggregates of the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) using an empirical relationship based on field observations.</p>	
MAIN VARIABLES		
Name	Units (SI)	Description
ndvi	index [-1,+1]	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index based on Sentinel-2 bands 8 (NIR) and 4 (RED): $NDVI = (NIR - RED) / (NIR + RED)$
vegetation_percent_cover	%	percent cover of vegetation
n_obs	count	number of available observations used for the aggregation
SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY		
Algorithm description:	<p>The evolved algorithm computes percent cover of emerging aquatic vegetation (seagrass and macroalgae) in intertidal regions of the German Bight based on temporal aggregates of the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). Sentinel-2 data are atmospherically corrected using sen2cor and pixels identified as water or clouds using IdePix are masked. Images are processed and aggregated using the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem. Retrieved NDVI values are temporally aggregated per pixel around the time of maximum seagrass cover in July/August/September. Aggregated NDVI values are translated into vegetation percent cover based on an empirical relationship.</p>	
Limitations:	<p>Data availability depends on water level at the time of satellite acquisitions and cloud cover and may therefore vary spatially and temporally. The algorithm does not enable differentiation between different types of emerging aquatic vegetation (e.g., macroalgae, seagrass, diatoms) and does not consider</p>	

	vegetation health. This information would be subject of further development based on the delivered products.
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
format_version	"v0.1"
title	Emerged seagrass and macroalgae
summary	"High spatial resolution emerged from aquatic vegetation products derived from Sentinel-2 data. Covers intertidal mudflats along the shoreline of the German Bight during low-tide. Uses temporally aggregated observations of the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index."
project	13800
source_platform_category_code	"Satellite"
phase	"Technology validated in relevant environment"
platform	"Sentinel-2 A", "Sentinel-2 B"
platform_type	"low earth orbit satellite"
platform_vocabulary	"CEOS"
instrument	"MSI"
instrument_vocabulary	"CEOS"
institution	"Brockmann Consult GmbH"
references	Zoffoli, M.L., Gernez, P., Rosa, P., Le Bris, A., Brando, V.E., Barillé, A.L., Harin, N., Peters, S., Poser, K., Spaias, L., Peralta, G., Barillé, L., 2020. Sentinel-2 remote sensing of Zostera noltei-dominated intertidal seagrass meadows. Remote Sens. Environ. 251, 112020. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.112020
product_version	"0.1"
version_date	"2025-02-28T00:30:00Z"
keywords	"FOCCUS; Copernicus; Coastal; Seagrass; Macroalgae; intertidal"
keywords_vocabulary	"NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Science Keywords"
comment	"First version of the emerged vegetation coverage"
area	"German Bight"
cdm_data_type	"grid"
time_coverage_resolution	P1Y
time_coverage_duration	P3M
geospatial_lat_min	53.23
geospatial_lat_max	55.62
geospatial_lat_units	"degree_north"
geospatial_lon_min	6.54
geospatial_lon_max	9.31
geospatial_lon_units	"degree_east"
geospatial_vertical_min	"0"
geospatial_vertical_max	"0"
geospatial_vertical_units	"metres above mean sea level"
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
grid_resolution	"10 m"
update_interval	"void"

processing_level	"L4"
creator_name	"0000-0002-7617-888X"
creator_url	"https://www.brockmann-consult.de/"
contributor_name	"0000-0003-4859-2204; 0000-0003-0831-6520; 0000-0002-2195-4327; 0000-0003-1892-0051; 0009-0006-8984-1157"
contributor_url	"https://www.ismar.cnr.it/"
contributor_email	"kerstin.stelzer@brockmann-consult.de, carole.lebreton@brockmann-consult.de, carsten.brockmann@brockmann-consult.de, laura.zoffoli@artov.ismar.cnr.it, juliamarie.braud@artov.ismar.cnr.it"
method	"Empirical approach, NDVI, Time-series aggregation"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	"marcel.koenig@brockmann-consult.de"
technical_support_contact	"marcel.koenig@brockmann-consult.de"
USE CASES	
Overview	The dataset can be integrated into hydrodynamic models to account for effects of aquatic vegetation on wave height, water level, morphodynamics and coastal erosion.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User - HEREON FOCCUS Model - SCHISM-WWM-Xbeach with AI FOCCUS Application - Coastal erosion dynamics, Coastal management
KEY REFERENCES	
Zoffoli, M.L., Gernez, P., Rosa, P., Le Bris, A., Brando, V.E., Barillé, A.L., Harin, N., Peters, S., Poser, K., Spaias, L., Peralta, G., Barillé, L., 2020. Sentinel-2 remote sensing of Zostera noltei-dominated intertidal seagrass meadows. Remote Sens. Environ. 251, 112020. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.112020	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.	

4.6.2 Submerged seagrass and macroalgae

	derived from temporally aggregated Sentinel-2 data along the coast of the Balearic Islands using machine learning methods, semi-analytical model inversion or a combination of both."
source_platform_category_code	"Satellite"
platform	"Sentinel-2 A", "Sentinel-2 B"
platform_type	"low earth orbit satellite"
platform_vocabulary	"CEOS"
instrument	"MSI"
instrument_vocabulary	"CEOS"
institution	"Brockmann Consult GmbH"
references	Chowdhury, M., Martínez-Sansigre, A., Mole, M. et al., 2024, AI-driven remote sensing enhances Mediterranean seagrass monitoring and conservation to combat climate change and anthropogenic impacts. Sci Rep 14, 8360. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-59091-7
product_version	"0.1"
version_date	"2025-02-28T00:30:00Z"
comment	"First version of the submerged vegetation coverage"
area	"Balearic Islands"
cdm_data_type	"grid"
time_coverage_resolution	P1Y
time_coverage_duration	P12M
geospatial_lat_min	38.56
geospatial_lat_max	40.12
geospatial_lat_units	"degree_north"
geospatial_lon_min	1.13
geospatial_lon_max	4.37
geospatial_lon_units	"degree_east"
geospatial_vertical_min	"0"
geospatial_vertical_max	"0"
geospatial_vertical_units	"metres above mean sea level"
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
grid_resolution	"10 m"
update_interval	"void"
date_created	"2025-02-28T00:30:00Z"
processing_level	"L4"
creator_name	"0000-0002-7617-888X"
creator_url	" https://www.brockmann-consult.de/ "
contributor_name	"0000-0003-4859-2204; 0000-0003-0831-6520; 0000-0002-2195-4327; 0000-0003-1892-0051; 0009-0006-8984-1157"
contributor_url	" https://www.ismar.cnr.it/ "
contributor_email	"kerstin.stelzer@brockmann-consult.de, carole.lebreton@brockmann-consult.de, carsten.brockmann@brockmann-consult.de, laura.zoffoli@artov.ismar.cnr.it,"

	juliamarie.braud@artov.ismar.cnr.it"
method	"Machine learning approach, Time-series aggregation"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	"marcel.koenig@brockmann-consult.de"
technical_support_contact	"marcel.koenig@brockmann-consult.de"
USE CASES	
Overview	The dataset can be integrated into hydrodynamic models to account for effects of aquatic vegetation on wave height, water level and morphodynamics. It can also be used to improve the understanding of accumulation of beach wrack and sensitivity of methods for satellite-derived bathymetry.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User - SOCIB FOCCUS Model - GCOAST-BS FOCCUS Application - Coastal erosion dynamics, Coastal management, Satellite-derived bathymetry, Beach wrack position
KEY REFERENCES	
Chowdhury, M., Martínez-Sansigre, A., Mole, M. et al., 2024, AI-driven remote sensing enhances Mediterranean seagrass monitoring and conservation to combat climate change and anthropogenic impacts. Sci Rep 14, 8360. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-59091-7	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.	

4.7. Beach monitoring

4.7.1 High-resolution topobathymetries

HIGH-RESOLUTION TOPOBATHYMETRIES		
	OVERVIEW: Gridded coastal topographic and bathymetric surveys (continuous data-fusion). Two primary data products are provided: Very high-resolution irregular-gridded datasets (grid-as-point) with a best point spacing of ~1 m (shapefiles), and interpolated gridded datasets with a spatial resolution of 10 m (NetCDF). Products are delivered in the form of time series of topo bathymetries for beaches in the Balearic Islands and the Romanian coast in separate files for each site and type of data product.	
MAIN VARIABLES		
Name	Units (SI)	Description (long name)
LAT (Mandatory)	degree_north	Latitude is positive northward (latitude)
LON (Mandatory)	degree_east	Longitude is positive eastward (longitude)
TIME (Mandatory)	days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00Z	Time measured in days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC using the gregorian calendar (time)

ALT (Mandatory)	m	The -geometric- height above the geoid, which is the reference geopotential surface (altitude above the geoid)
ALT_SD (Recommended)	m	standard deviation of measurements that contributed to the node (cell standard deviation)
QC (Mandatory)	1	Indicator of assessed quality information of altitude (quality flag)

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	Dry beach topography and shallow water surveys (~2 m to -1.2 m) are conducted with RTK-GNSS systems. Bathymetric data from ~1.2 to 10-15 m derives from Multibeam Echo-sounder measurements. All data is subjected to a quality control involving both manual (interactive) and automatic (non-interactive) tasks prior merging. These procedures involve correcting data (e.g., angle misalignments, vertical offset), removing data (i.e., outliers), and flagging data according to QC tests. Data is thinned using common statistics (e.g., mean, median, minimum) and grid gaps are filled in the interpolated product.
Limitations:	The data is provided without any warranty, either explicit or implied, including warranties of merchantability or fitness for a specific purpose. The data should not be used for navigation or any purpose relating to safety at sea. Compared to echo-sounder data, topographic surveys performed using RTK (in V/U-shaped profiles) have a lower density.

METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)

GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:

format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Cala Millor beach gridded and interpolated topobathymetries from in-situ measurements"
summary	The dataset includes a time series of Cala Millor beach topographic and bathymetric surveys, gridded on a 10 m grid. Topographic surveys and most shallow waters were surveyed using RTK-GNSS, and multibeam echo-sounder was used for the remaining depths.
source_platform_category_code	"self-propelled boat; human"
platform	"Valiant DR 620; human"
platform_type	"research vessel; human"
platform_vocabulary	"SeaVoX Platform Categories" and http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/
instrument	R2Sonic 2020 multibeam echosounder; Septentrio Altus RTK-GNSS; Leica GS10 RTK-GNSS; GEOMAX Zenith60 RTK-GNSS
instrument_vocabulary	"BODC"
institution	"Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System"
institution_edmo_code	"3410"

references	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02210-2
product_version	"1.0"
comment	Topographic and bathymetric surveys were processed to correct, filter, and flag raw full-density data. The post-processing stage involved data point density reduction (thinning) and interpolation. Detailed information regarding the data set's development and the inclusion of source data sets within the grid can be found in the data set documentation.
area	Mediterranean Sea
cdm_data_type	grid
geospatial_lat_min	39.5877339774644
geospatial_lat_max	39.6028839774644
geospatial_lon_min	3.38424740769587
geospatial_lon_max	3.39154740769587
geospatial_vertical_min	-15
geospatial_vertical_max	2
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"1"
grid_resolution	"10 m"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"L4"
creator_name	0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924
creator_url	"https://socib.es"
contributor_name	0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924
method	"in-situ measurements, quality control, gridding, and interpolation"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	"mobims@socib.es"
technical_support_contact	"datacenter@socib.es"
USE CASES	
Overview	The dataset allows the user to model morphodynamics, identify areas of deposition and erosion, evaluate sediment balance, coastal overtopping and flooding, coastal interventions and management, and to conduct cal/val exercises related to satellite-derived topography and bathymetry.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User - SOCIB, +ATLANTIC, CNR, BC FOCCUS Model - GCOAST-BS FOCCUS Application - Coastal erosion, Multi-use of off-shore installations, Storm surges, coastal flooding
KEY REFERENCES	
Fernández-Mora, A., Criado-Sudau, F.F., Gómez-Pujol, L. <i>et al.</i> Ten years of morphodynamic data at a micro-tidal urban beach: Cala Millor (Western Mediterranean Sea). <i>Sci Data</i> 10 , 301 (2023).	

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02210-2>

ICTS SOCIB Data Repository; editing status 2024-06-21; re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. <http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJMPH>

HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?

The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025

4.7.2 Waves

WAVES PARAMETERS

OVERVIEW: The In-situ near-shore wave data product is integrated in the 'Near-shore Beach Data products', designed to deliver key physical variables for comprehensive coastal monitoring. By capturing detailed information on wave climate, this product complements other data sets, such as shoreline position, sediment transport, and sea level, providing a holistic view of the nearshore environment.

Considering the existing and available dataset in the strategic areas, the wave data product has been designed considering CMEMS standards and the instrumentation type, which defines the type of analysis developed on computing variables from raw measurements and which variables can be delivered.

Quality control procedures have been applied to key mandatory variables.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description
TIME	days since 1950-01-01 T00:00:00Z	M
LATITUDE	degree_north	M
LONGITUDE	degree_east	M
DEPH	m	M
VGHS, VHM0, SWHT, VAVH	m	M ⁶ - sea surface significant wave height
VEMH, VZMX, VCMX	m	M ¹ - sea surface wave maximum height
VTZA, VTGA	s	M ¹ - sea surface wave mean period
VTPK	s	M - wave period at spectral peak
VMDR, VDIR	degree	M ¹ - sea surface wave from direction
VPSP	degree	M - wave directional spreading at spectral peak
QC and other optional variables:	Report T2.1.4 Design of beach monitoring products	

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	Instrument Depending Algorithms: unknown (generic variables), spectral analysis, zero-crossing. QC procedures applied.
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⁶ At least, one of the type of variables should be considered

Limitations:	No limitations considered
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:	
format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Data from instrument SCB-WAVE003 on platform Buoy BahiaDePalma"
summary	"This dataset stands for the aggregated near real time data from the Oceanographic Moored buoy at Bahía de Palma "
source_platform_category_code	"41; moored surface buoy"
platform	41
platform_type	"moored surface buoy"
platform_vocabulary	"BODC"
instrument	"BRIZO-X"
instrument_vocabulary	"BODC"
institution	"Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System"
institution_edmo_code	"3410"
references	—
product_version	"1.0"
comment	"Wave height sensor using GPS and GLONASS L1&L2 signals designed to store data internally or interface with an external datalogger. GNSS antenna mounted internally"
geospatial_lat_min	39.492848
geospatial_lat_max	39.492848
geospatial_lon_min	2.700405
geospatial_lon_max	2.700405
geospatial_vertical_min	0
geospatial_vertical_max	0
geospatial_vertical_positive	"down"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"void"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"L1"
creator_name	"0000-0002-6311-0093; 0000-0002-3978-3255"
creator_url	"https://socib.es"
contributor_name	"0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924"
method	"Spectral Analysis; zero-crossing"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	"mobims@socib.es"
technical_support_contact	"datacenter@socib.es"
USE CASES	
Overview	The intended use of this data is to: provides real-time and localised information for beach safety, navigation, and recreational activities; support decision-making for coastal infrastructure and flood risk management, enhance the accuracy

	of wave and coastal models by providing precise calibration and validation data (hindcast and forecast models), improves predictive capabilities for coastal hazards, erosion, and sediment transport, supports early warning systems for storms and coastal flooding, assist in designing coastal adaptation methods and sustainable beach management practices and inform climate change impact studies on coastal environments.
Benefits for user/model/application	<p>FOCCUS User: Researchers, Coastal managers, Emergency Systems</p> <p>FOCCUS Model: GCOAST-GB, GCOAST-BS</p> <p>FOCCUS Application: Coastal erosion, Storm surges, Wave climate, coastal flooding</p>
KEY REFERENCES	
<p>Fernández-Mora, A., Criado-Sudau, F.F., Gómez-Pujol, L. <i>et al.</i> Ten years of morphodynamic data at a micro-tidal urban beach: Cala Millor (Western Mediterranean Sea). <i>Sci Data</i> 10, 301 (2023). https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02210-2</p> <p>ICTS SOCIB Data Repository; editing status 2024-06-21; re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJMPH</p>	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025	

4.7.3 Sea level

SEA LEVEL		
	<p>OVERVIEW: The In-situ sea level (tide gauge) data product is integrated in the 'Near-shore Beach Data products', designed to deliver key physical variables for comprehensive coastal monitoring. By capturing detailed information on sea level, this product complements other data sets, such as shoreline position, sediment transport, and waves, providing a holistic view of the nearshore environment.</p> <p>Considering the existing and available dataset in the strategic areas, the sea level data product has been designed considering CMEMS standards. Quality control procedures have been applied to key mandatory variables.</p>	
MAIN VARIABLES		
Name	Units (SI)	Description
TIME	days since 1950-01-01T00:00:00Z	M
LATITUDE	degree_north	Latitude of measurement
LONGITUDE	degree_east	Longitude of measurement
SLEV	m	Water surface height above a specific datum

SLEV_QC	flag	Water surface height above a specific datum quality flag
ATMS	hPa	Atmospheric pressure at sea level
ATMS_QC	flag	Atmospheric pressure at sea level quality flag
QC and other optional variables:	Report T2.1.4 Design of beach monitoring products	

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	The method of calculating sea level varies by sensor type. If the station has both a water pressure gauge and an atmospheric pressure sensor, the hydrostatic equation is used to determine the water column height above the pressure sensor. By referencing the sensor's position relative to the geoid, the absolute sea level measurement can be obtained. On the other hand, radars directly measure water level by determining the elapsed time between the emission of short microwave pulses and their return. In this pulse procedure, a brief microwave impulse is sent to the water surface. The transmitter has a short delay, allowing the water to transmit the pulses to the integrated evaluation system. The pulse runtime directly corresponds to the distance to the actual water surface level.
Limitations:	No limitations considered

METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)

GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:	
format_version	"v0.1"
title	In situ sea level
summary	"Near real-time sea level observations from tide gauges in the Balearic Islands and the Black Sea, collected from 2011 to 2024 and 2021 to 2024, respectively. It includes the water surface height above specific datum measurements at sub-hourly and hourly resolutions."
source_platform_category_code	"Coastal structure"
phase	"Operational"
platform	"Coastal structure"
platform_type	"Land or seafloor"
platform_vocabulary	"BODC"
instrument	"Radar Water Level Recorder, Sea-Bird SBE 26plus SEAGAUGE Wave and Tide Recorder, Vaisala PTB330 digital barometer"
instrument_vocabulary	"BODC"
institution	"Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System"
institution_edmo_code	"3410"
references	http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-854 , http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-1444
product_version	"1.0"
comment	"Depending on the platform's sensor, sea level is determined either through direct distance measurement to the water surface"

	or by applying the hydrostatic equation”
area	“Balearic Islands and Black Sea”
geospatial_lat_min	“39.25, 43.74”
geospatial_lat_max	“40.10, 45.15 ”
geospatial_lon_min	“2.30, 28.55”
geospatial_lon_max	“4.45, 29.8”
geospatial_vertical_min	“0”
geospatial_vertical_max	“0”
geospatial_vertical_positive	“down”
geospatial_vertical_resolution	“point”
update_interval	“600 seconds”
processing_level	“L1”
creator_name	“0000-0002-6311-0093; 0000-0002-3978-3255”
creator_url	“https://socib.es”
contributor_name	“0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924”
contributor_url	“https://socib.es”
contributor_email	“mobims@socib.es”
method	“instantaneous values”
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	“mobims@socib.es”
technical_support_contact	“etd@socib.es”
USE CASES	
Overview	This near real-time sea level dataset provides critical information for monitoring coastal changes in the Balearic Islands and the Black Sea. The high-resolution measurements allow for the analysis of sea level fluctuations, storm and extreme event impacts, and long-term trends. This data is essential for assessing coastal flood risk, coastal erosion, understanding sea level rise implications, and supporting effective coastal management strategies.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User: Researchers, Coastal managers, Emergency Systems. FOCCUS Model GCOAST-BS. FOCCUS Application Coastal erosion, flooding, storm surges.
KEY REFERENCES	
Copernicus Marine in Situ tac Data Management Team (2024). Copernicus Marine In Situ TAC - physical parameters list. Copernicus Marine In Situ TAC. https://doi.org/10.13155/53381 UNESCO/IOC (2020) Quality Control of in situ Sea Level Observations: A Review and Progress towards Automated Quality Control, Vol. 1. (eds. Pérez Gómez, B., et al). Paris, France, UNESCO, 70pp. (IOC Manuals and Guides No.83, Vol. 1). (IOC/2020/MG/83Vol.1). DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.25607/OBP-854	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025	

4.7.4 Shoreline position

SHORELINE POSITION

OVERVIEW: High resolution shoreline positions measured in-situ with RTK (Real-Time Kinematic) and image-derived ones from beach imaging systems products (manually digitised). The dataset provides a time series of multipoint geometries (xyz) in a shapefile. Each row or feature in the shapefile represents the shoreline at a specific time and location, including beaches in the Balearic Islands and the Romanian coast.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description (long name)
LAT (Mandatory)	degree north	Latitude is positive northward (latitude)
LON (Mandatory)	degree east	Longitude is positive eastward (longitude)
TIME (Mandatory)	days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00Z	Time measured in days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC using the gregorian calendar (time)
ALT (Mandatory)	m	The -geometric- height above the geoid, which is the reference geopotential surface (altitude above the geoid)
SHRL_ID (Mandatory)	1	Proxy to represent the shoreline position (shoreline proxy)
PLTF_ID (Mandatory)	1	Identifies the platform from which an observation was made (platform_id)
PLTF_N (Mandatory)	1	Station description such as the geographical place (platform_name).
QC (Mandatory)	1	Indicator of assessed quality information of positioning (quality flag).
Other optional variables	Report T2.1.4 Design of beach monitoring products	

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	Instantaneous waterline position either measured with RTK-GNSS systems or derived from land-based imaging systems. To produce image-derived shorelines, oblique images from each site are spatially coregistered, and rectified (projected to a terrain coordinate system) using photogrammetric algorithms. Shorelines are manually digitalized on the resulting planview. All shorelines undergo expert supervision (quality control).
Limitations:	Shoreline positions are delivered at irregular intervals across various sites. Shoreline points are not equidistant across all sites and timestamps. Additionally, the positioning accuracy of image-derived shoreline points may degrade with increasing distance to the camera.

METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)

GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:

format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Instantaneous shoreline position data from in-situ RTK-GNSS measurements and land-based beach imaging systems"
summary	The dataset includes a time series of instantaneous shoreline positions at Cala Millor beach. The instantaneous shoreline is the position of the waterline (swash uprush limit) at one instant in time, measured with RTK-GNSS or derived from rectified beach images.
source_platform_category_code	"land/onshore structure; human"
platform	"building; human"
platform_type	"land/onshore structure; human"
platform_vocabulary	"BODC"
instrument	"DFK 41AF02 Color Camera; Leica GS10 RTK-GNSS; GEOMAX Zenith60 RTK-GNSS"
instrument_vocabulary	"BODC"
institution	"Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System"
institution_edmo_code	"3410"
references	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02210-2
product_version	"1.0"
version_date	"YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"
comment	The Cala Millor beach video-monitoring system consists of 5 RGB cameras mounted at the top of a building (elevation ~ 47 m) at the beachfront. Cameras take oblique pictures of the beach (1280x960 px) with overlapping sights. Images are rectified to a terrain coordinate system using photogrammetric algorithms, and shoreline points are manually digitised by the scientist in charge. The RTK-GNSS data comes from topographic campaigns. All collected shorelines undergo a process of review and filtering. Detailed information regarding the data set's development and the quality control performed can be found in the data set documentation.
geospatial_lat_min	39.5891481005203687
geospatial_lat_max	39.6018117647248360
geospatial_lon_min	3.3842558134392791
geospatial_lon_max	3.3866966557462623
geospatial_vertical_min	-
geospatial_vertical_max	-
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"1"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"L3"
creator_name	0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924
creator_url	"https://socib.es"
contributor_name	0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924

method	“in-situ measurements and quality control; or, image processing (photogrammetry) and shoreline digitalization (manual)”
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	“mobims@socib.es”
technical_support_contact	“datacenter@socib.es”
USE CASES	
Overview	The shoreline position serves as an integrated and fundamental proxy in the fields of coastal research, engineering, and management. The dataset allows the user to study the spatiotemporal dynamics of beach behaviour, and the erosion and accretion trends at different time scales, their impact in coastal evolution, and has applications in cal/val exercises related to satellite-derived shorelines.
Benefits user/model/application	for FOCCUS User - SOCIB, MHD, +ATLANTIC FOCCUS Model - GCOAST-BS FOCCUS Application - Coastal erosion, Combating degradation of ecosystems, Storm surges, coastal flooding
KEY REFERENCES	
<p>Fernàndez-Mora, À., Criado, F. F., Gómez, L., Tintoré, J., Orfila, A. (2023). Ten years of morphodynamic data at a micro-tidal urban beach: Cala Millor (Western Mediterranean Sea). <i>Scientific Data</i>, 10(301). 10.1038/s41597-023-02210-2.</p> <p>González-Villanueva, R., Sánchez, E., Soriano, J. (2023). SCShores: time-series of shorelines from Spanish Sandy beaches from citizen-science monitoring program [Dataset]. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.8056415</p> <p>González-Villanueva, R., Soriano, J., Alejo, I., Criado, F. F., Palomaritis, T., Fernàndez-Mora, À., Benavente, J., Del, L., Nombela, A., & Sánchez, E. (2023). SCShores: a comprehensive shoreline dataset of Spanish sandy beaches from a citizen-science monitoring programme. <i>Earth System Science Data</i>.</p> <p>Harley, M. D., Kinsela, M. A., Sánchez-García, E., Vos, K. (2019). Shoreline change mapping using crowd-sourced smartphone images, <i>Coast. Eng.</i>, 150, 175–189.</p> <p>Nieto, M.A., Garau, B., Balle, S., Simarro, G., Zarruk, G.A., Ortiz, A., Tintoré, J., Álvarez-Ellacuría, A., Gómez-Pujol, L. and Orfila, A. (2010). An open source, low cost video-based coastal monitoring system. <i>Earth Surf. Process. Landforms</i>, 35, 1712-1719.</p>	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.	

4.7.5. Total water level

TOTAL WATER LEVEL

OVERVIEW: The Total Water Level (TWL) dataset for the Portuguese continental coast provides an hourly time series from 1994 to 2022. The TWL is computed using a linear summation equation that considers the wave runup, astronomical tides, storm surges and sea level anomalies to model coastal water levels. By integrating multiple dynamic components, the TWL dataset provides a comprehensive insight of coastal exposure to extreme events such as flooding and overtopping, supporting coastal risk management.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description (long name)
LAT (Mandatory)	degree_north	Latitude is positive northward (latitude)
LON (Mandatory)	degree_east	Longitude is positive eastward (longitude)
TIME (Mandatory)	days since 1950-01-01 00:00:00Z	Time measured in days since 1950-01-01 00:00:00 UTC using the gregorian calendar (time)
TWL (Mandatory)	m	Total sea level: R + AT + SS + SLA
ID (Mandatory)	1	Proxy to represent the time series position
R (Optional)	m	Wave runup (R) estimation using Stockdon et al., 2006 empirical formula using wave parameters from WAVERYS reanalysis and slope from Athanasius, 2019
AT (Optional)	m	Astronomical Tide - FES2014 using pyfes package
SS (Optional)	m	Storm Surge - Dynamic atmospheric correction (DAC) from Mog2D HR barotropic model output combined with Inverted Barometer correction, system version 2.0.0
SLA (Optional)	m	Sea Level Anomaly - 1 Hz X-TRACK-L2P Sea Level Anomalies v2.0 - CTOH/LEGOS
Other optional variables	Report T2.1.4 Design of beach monitoring products	

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:

The linear summation empirical modelling downscaling (LSDW) approach integrates multi-data sources (EO-products, hindcast datasets) together with empirical formulations for the prediction of the interaction between the extreme sea levels and nearshore morphology. This approach accounts for all the local sea level components, even though it does not reproduce their nonlinear interactions. This methodological approach has been widely used for local (Almeida et al., 2018), regional (Melet et al., 2016) and global (Almar et al., 2021), long-term reconstruction and projection of

	extreme sea levels, demonstrating to be a good choice for upscaling.
Limitations:	The LSDW approach considers the coastal morphology static along the time, and erosion due to waves or currents is not considered. Additionally, the TWL time series is delivered at irregular intervals across Portugal beaches.
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:	
format_version	"v1.0"
netcdf_version	"4.4.1.1"
title	"Total Water Level"
summary	"This dataset was computed using multi-source datasets and linear summation approach for a single point at the coast"
source_platform_category_code	"satellite; reanalysis; model"
platform	"Multimission Altimeter Satellite - Topex/Jason-1/Jason-2/Jason-3/ERS-1/ERS-2/ Envisat/SARAL/AltiKa/GFO/Sentinel-3A/Haiyang-2A; CMEMS (Mercator Océan International); AVISO+"
platform_type	"satellite; modelling"
platform_vocabulary	"CEOS"
instrument	radar altimeter; modelling
instrument_vocabulary	"CEOS"
institution	"+ATLANTIC CoLAB"
institution_edmo_code	"5952"
references	-
product_version	"1.0"
version_date	"YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"
comment	"Total Water Level (TWL) computed using linear summation approach"
time_coverage_start	1994-01-01 00:00:00
time_coverage_end	2021-12-31 21:00:00
time_coverage_resolution	hourly
geospatial_lat_min	36.90
geospatial_lat_max	41.90
geospatial_lon_min	-9.51
geospatial_lon_max	-7.40
geospatial_vertical_min	-
geospatial_vertical_max	-
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
geospatial_vertical_units	"meters above or below mean sea level"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"L4"
creator_name	https://orcid.org/0009-0009-2108-7639

creator_url	"https://colabatlantic.com"
contributor_name	0000-0001-5878-3317 - 0009-0009-2108-7639
method	"The linear summation empirical modelling downscaling (LSDW) approach"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	"pedro.almeida@colabatlantic.com"
technical_support_contact	"atlanticsense@colabatlantic.com"
USE CASES	
Overview	The TWL represents the elevation at the shoreline, incorporating the combined effects of astronomical tides, storm surge, relative sea level rise, and wave runup. This metric is essential for assessing potential coastal erosion and flooding risks. The data allows the user to analyse historical coastal sea level patterns, identify extreme events, and assess the potential for coastal erosion, for example, computing indexes that generate degrees of exposure of the beach.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User - +ATLANTIC FOCCUS User - Researchers, Coastal managers, Emergency Systems. FOCCUS Application - Coastal erosion, storm surges, coastal flooding.
KEY REFERENCES	
Almar, R., Ranasinghe, R., Bergsma, E. W. J., et al. (2021). A global analysis of extreme coastal water levels with implications for potential coastal overtopping. Nature Communications, 12, Article 3775. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-24008-9	
Stockdon, H. F., Long, J. W., Palmsten, M. L., et al. (2023). Operational forecasts of wave-driven water levels and coastal hazards for US Gulf and Atlantic coasts. Communications Earth & Environment, 4, Article 169. https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-00817-2	
Melet, A., Almar, R., Hemer, M., Le Cozannet, G., Meyssignac, B., & Ruggiero, P. (2020). Contribution of wave setup to projected coastal sea level changes. Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans, 125(8). https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JC016078	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.	

4.8. Surface currents

SURFACE CURRENTS

OVERVIEW: 2D surface total currents reconstructed at an hourly and 5 by 5 km resolution. Data will be tallied at some coastal sites with HF radar in the Mediterranean Sea.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description
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EWCT	m s ⁻¹	Eastward sea water velocity at the surface
NSCT	m s ⁻¹	Northward sea water velocity at the surface
LATITUDElatitude	degree_north	Latitude
LONGITUDElongitude	degree_east	Longitude
TIMEtime	hours since 1950-01-01 00:00:00 UTC	Time

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	The objective is to analyse the feasibility of a machine learning/deep learning algorithm to reconstruct vectorial total surface velocities at an hourly resolution. The model will be learned from a numerical model with velocities at a 1/12° spatial resolution as outputs and at least SSH, winds, SST and SSS variables as inputs. Therefore, the inference will be done from satellite observations and among them SWOT-Karin data. Finally the results will be compared with HF radar total velocities and drifters where available. The training and inference will be done on some sites where HF Radar data are available over the Mediterranean Sea.
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Limitations:	This approach can be limited by inconsistency between the numerical model and the satellite observations, the remaining errors in SWOT data and the time/space coverage of the swaths, the skills of ML/DL to capture the total velocities variability in different coastal regions where the dynamic could be very specific. The method is new and does not guarantee total success early in the project. The development will be undertaken as a Proof of concept.
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METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)

format_version	"v0.1"
conventions	"CF-1.6"
title	"total surface velocities from machine learning algorithm"
summary	"Ocean surface total velocities product derived from a machine learning approach that merges model reanalysis, satellite observations, ERA5 winds and HF radars. The product covers some Mediterranean Sea coastal regions where HF radars are available. The final data are geospatial grids with zonal and meridional velocity fields."
project	13800
source_platform_category_code	"satellite; model; coastal structure"
platform	"satellite, coastal structure"
platform_type	"satellite, high-frequency radar"
platform_vocabulary	"CEOS"
Instrument	"--"
instrument_vocabulary	"--"

band	"_"
polarization	"_"
radar_wavenumber	"_"
institution	CLS (Collecte Localisation satellite)
institution_edmo_code	5934
references	"1.0"
version_date	"YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"
keywords	"FOCCUS; Copernicus; Coastal; Ocean; Ocean currents".
area	"Mediterranean Sea"
geospatial_lat_min	example: "-89.875"
geospatial_lat_max	example: "89.875"
geospatial_lat_units	"degree_north"
geospatial_lon_min	example: "-179.875"
geospatial_lon_max	example: "179.875"
geospatial_lon_units	"degree_east"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"0"
grid_resolution	"5 km"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	To be defined in the D2.2 (February 2025)
creator_name	https://orcid.org/0009-0001-5702-8536
creator_url	" https://www.cls.fr "
contributor_name	0009-0001-5702-8536, 0009-0003-3245-9545, 0009-0008-8666-3812, 0009-0002-7113-2572
contributor_url	"DataManager"
contributor_email	"nverbrugge@groupcls.com"
method	"Artificial intelligence"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
USE CASES	
Overview	The product can be used for monitoring of the total ocean surface currents with a 5 kilometres resolution. Thanks to high spatial resolution these observations of the ocean surface current provide an opportunity for studying ocean dynamics processes in the coastal areas such as eddies and filaments. It could also provide an independent dataset for validation/intercomparison of/with the coastal models.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User. The product can be used by the scientific community for studying mesoscale ocean circulation processes in the coastal areas and for independent validation or intercomparison with model numerical data. FOCCUS Model. The product could be used by the coastal modelling community for validation/intercomparison of high resolution WMOP (developed by SOCIB) ocean forecasting systems in the regions delivered over the coastal Mediterranean Sea.

	<p>FOCCUS Application. The product can lead to the benefits regarding following FOCCUS applications:</p> <p>ESC1 - Pollution hazard - the product can enhance the ocean current forecasting and validation leading to better forecasting and response to the pollution hazards</p> <p>ESC2 - Multi-use of off-shore installations - the product can participate in the environmental analysis necessary for off-shore installations.</p> <p>ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding - the use of the product by relevant intermediate users can improve our understanding and forecasting of extreme coastal events</p>
<p>KEY REFERENCES</p>	
<p>N/A</p>	
<p>HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?</p>	
<p>The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025</p>	

4.9. Harmful algal blooms (HABs) probability

<h3>HABs probability</h3>		
	<p>OVERVIEW: The probability of detecting harmful algae blooms of toxic algae along the Norwegian coast. The toxic species corresponds to the ones monitored by the Norwegian Food Safety Authority (NFSA) in the mussel (<i>Mytilus edulis</i>) farms, which are <i>Dinophysis acuta</i> Ehrenberg 1839, <i>Alexandrium</i> Halim, 1960, <i>Alexandrium tamarense</i> (Lebour) Balech 1995, <i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> H. Peragallo, 1900, <i>Azadinium spinosum</i> Elbrächter & Tillmann 2009.</p> <p>The HAB probability is the probability of toxic algae exceeding harmful levels that can contaminate blue mussels with toxins (see variable description for each taxon).</p> <p>The probability is estimated using artificial intelligence models (Silva et al., 2024) that use as input the environmental conditions along the coastal waters, including sea surface temperature (SST), mixed layer depth (MLD), sea surface salinity (SSS), and photosynthetic active radiation (PAR).</p>	
<p>MAIN VARIABLES</p>		
Name	Units (SI)	Description
alexandrium_spp_hab	%	probability of <i>Alexandrium</i> spp. exceeding 200 cells/L
a_tamarense_hab	%	probability of <i>Alexandrium tamarense</i> group. exceeding 200 cells/L
d_acuta_hab	%	probability of <i>Dinophysis acuta</i> exceeding 200 cells/L

a_spinosum_hab	%	probability of <i>Azadinium spinosum</i> exceeding 3600 cells/L
SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY		
Algorithm description:	The probability is estimated using support vector machines (SVM) using as input weekly observations of SST, PAR, MLD, and SSS (Silva et al., 2024). SVM is calibrated with toxic algae observations from the NFSA monitoring program, which identify the toxic algae on the 0-3 m surface along 32 stations every week. The SST observations are from the ESA SST CCI and C3S global SST reprocessed product level 4, PAR observations are from the GlobColour project that uses Frouin et al. (2003) algorithm applied to MODIS, SeaWiFS, and VIIRS sensors, and MLD and SSS are from the CMEMS Arctic MFC TOPAZ modelling system.	
Limitations:	The coarse spatial resolution makes data unavailable in the inner and narrow fjords. HAB probability is not available for <i>D. acuminata</i> , <i>D. norvegica</i> , <i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> spp., and <i>P. reticulatum</i> due to poor model performance. Models are not able to estimate 100% probability as HABs depend on more factors than the ones currently used as input (SST, PAR, MLD, and SSS).	
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)		
GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:		
format_version	"v0.1"	
title	"Probability detection of harmful algae"	
summary	"The probability of harmful algae blooms (HAB) along the Norwegian coast given a sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity, mixed layer depth, and photosynthetically active radiation."	
source_platform_category_code	"--"	
platform	"--"	
platform_type	"--"	
platform_vocabulary	"--"	
instrument	"--"	
instrument_vocabulary	"--"	
institution	"Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center"	
institution_edmo_code	"1413"	
references	Silva, E., Brajard, J., Counillon, F., Pettersson, L. H., & Naustvoll, L. (2024). Probabilistic models for harmful algae: application to the Norwegian coast. <i>Environmental Data Science</i> , 3. https://doi.org/10.1017/eds.2024.11	
product_version	"1.0"	
comment	"Correlation between HAB probability and frequency is tested for the whole coast over 5 years (2014 - 2019)"	

cdm_data_type	"grid"
area	"Norwegian coast"
geospatial_lat_min	"55"
geospatial_lat_max	"75"
geospatial_lon_min	"0"
geospatial_lon_max	"40"
geospatial_vertical_min	"0"
geospatial_vertical_max	"1"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"--"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"L4"
creator_url	"https://nersc.no"
contributor_name	"0000-0002-1097-9801"
contributor_url	"Researcher"
contributor_email	"post@nersc.no"
method	"machine learning"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
USE CASES	
Overview	The HAB probability estimations can support shellfish farms and monitoring programs by mapping periods and regions with increased risk of HABs along the Norwegian coast. Farming and monitoring agencies can develop strategies based on this information for better allocating resources, improving health safety, and mitigating revenue losses.
Benefits for user/model/application	<p>FOCCUS User. Aquaculture farmers, fisheries managers, and environmental agencies in Norway can access these maps to assess the risk of HABs and take proactive measures to protect marine ecosystems and human health. For example, DELTARES, MET.NO, and HEREON</p> <p>FOCCUS Model. The integration of satellite, model reanalysis, and in-situ data enhances the accuracy and reliability of HAB prediction models, improving our understanding of bloom dynamics in the Norwegian coastal zone. Example of models are TOPAZ and NorKyst800</p> <p>FOCCUS Application. This application directly addresses the blue economy and following Essential Societal Challenges (ESCs):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ESC1 - Pollution hazard: By providing early warning of HABs, it helps mitigate the risks associated with these toxic events. ● ESC2 - Aquaculture/fisheries/energy sector: It supports sustainable aquaculture and fisheries management by providing risk assessment for informed decision-making. ● ESC3 - Combating ecosystem degradation: It contributes to the protection of marine ecosystems by enabling timely responses to HAB events.]
KEY REFERENCES	

Silva, E., Brajard, J., Counillon, F., Pettersson, L. H., & Naustvoll, L. (2024). Probabilistic models for harmful algae: application to the Norwegian coast. *Environmental Data Science*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1017/eds.2024.11>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10671482>.

HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?

The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025

4.10. Inland-marine water connectivity

Riverine Inherent optical properties

OVERVIEW:

Satellite-based Inherent optical properties (IOPs), such as absorption (a ; m^{-1}), backscattering (bb ; m^{-1}), water turbidity (WT; FNU) in river delta environments.

This set of products will diagnose inland-marine water connectivity by exploiting synergy between high-spatial resolution missions/sensor synergy, i.e., Sentinel-2 MSI and Sentinel-3 OLCI. While the multi-spectral characteristics and the daily based data availability of Sentinel-3 allow for a statistical robust analysis of these fundamental variables, the high spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 gives the rare opportunity to observe bio-optical properties of inland waters. Such a synergy allows for a synoptic reconstruction of spatial distribution of biogeochemical tracers and its human-induced changes, also recognizing inland and marine water connectivity in a source-to-sink fashion. The comparison among satellite-based IOPs from different sectors of the lower branch of the Po River (North Adriatic Sea) will provide links between Ocean Colour spectral signatures observed over delta/estuarine environments from Sentinel-2 MSI and over the related coastal zones from Sentinel-3 OLCI, allowing for a holistic/integrated analysis for recognizing and diagnosing inland-marine water connectivity and the related impacts on coastal environments, assessing the role of river inputs.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description
IOP absorption coefficient (a_{nw})	m^{-1}	Total non-water absorption coefficients at different wavelengths
IOP particulate backscattering coefficient (b_p)	m^{-1}	Particulate backscattering coefficient at different wavelengths
Water Turbidity (wt)	FNU	water turbidity expressed in formazin nephelometric unit

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	Algorithm description: “QAA-RGB semi-analytical algorithm for retrieving total absorption, particle backscattering, and water turbidity, from Sentinel2-MSI. QAA is a sequential flow of steps, some of which are empirical relationships between Rrs and some IOPs, whereas others follow from radiative transfer theory. A key initial step is the linkage of a predictor (χ ; unitless), derived from Rrs, to the non-water absorption coefficient at 555 nm, $a_{nw}(555)$. The band 555 nm is chosen because it is relatively insensitive to pigment variability. This step is similar to the derivation of chlorophyll from band ratios, as done in the OC algorithms. After $a_{nw}(555)$ retrieval, $b_p(555)$ is derived analytically by forcing Rrs closure. Then, bb is extended to the whole spectral range by assuming a power law spectral shape. Water turbidity is retrieved by using a semi-empirical single band algorithm that relates turbidity and marine reflectance at wavelength λ , from the water-leaving radiance and the above-water downwelling irradiance.
Limitations:	Cloud cover
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
format_version	“v0.1”
title	“Satellite-based Inherent optical properties (IOPs) in riverine environment”
summary	Satellite-based Inherent optical properties (IOPs), such as absorption (a_{nw} ; m^{-1}) and backscattering (bp ; m^{-1}), as well as water turbidity (WT; FNU) in river delta environments
source_platform_category_code	“satellite”
platform	“Sentinel-2A, Sentinel-2B, Sentinel-2C”
platform_type	“low earth orbit satellite”
platform_vocabulary	“CEOS”
instrument	“MSI”
instrument_vocabulary	“CEOS”
institution	“CNR-ISMAR”
institution_edmo_code	“227”
references	<p>Pitarch, J., & Vanhellemont, Q. (2021). The QAA-RGB: A universal three-band absorption and backscattering retrieval algorithm for high resolution satellite sensors. Development and implementation in ACOLITE. Remote Sensing of Environment, 265, 112667.</p> <p>Dogliotti, A. I., Ruddick, K. G., Nechad, B., Doxaran, D., & Knaeps, E. (2015). A single algorithm to retrieve turbidity from remotely-sensed data in all coastal and estuarine waters. Remote sensing of environment, 156, 157-168.</p> <p>Braga, F., Ciani, D., Colella, S., Organelli, E., Pitarch, J., Brando, V. E., ... & Falcini, F. (2022). COVID-19 lockdown effects on a coastal marine environment: Disentangling perception versus reality.</p>

	Science of the Total Environment, 817, 153002.
product_version	"1.0"
comment	"First version of IOPs in riverine environment"
area	"Po River Delta"
geospatial_lat_min	44.96°
geospatial_lat_max	44.96°
geospatial_lon_min	12.49°
geospatial_lon_max	12.49°
geospatial_vertical_min	0
geospatial_vertical_max	0
geospatial_vertical_positive	0
geospatial_vertical_resolution	–
grid_resolution	–
update_interval	P1Y
processing_level	L2
creator_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0239-0033
creator_url	https://www.ismar.cnr.it/
contributor_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0239-0033 https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7066-9258 https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3562-7180
contributor_url	https://www.ismar.cnr.it/
contributor_email	federico.falcini@cnr.it
method	satellite data processing
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	gSDK@artov.ismar.cnr.it
technical_support_contact	gSDK@artov.ismar.cnr.it
USE CASES	
Overview	<p>Users have highlighted the need for high- and hyper-resolution satellite products for coastal applications, to synoptically reconstruct the spatial distribution of PHYS, BGC, and sedimentary tracers, as well as anthropogenic inputs and environmental patterns, recognizing inland and marine water connectivity in a source-to-sink fashion (Braga et al., 2022). The scope of this product, therefore, is to assess water quality and bio-optical properties of riverine waters from ocean colour, satellite-based observations, allowing the scientific community, policy makers and the society in general to gather an observation-based consciousness of the impact (or lack of impact) of human activities affecting inland waters and marine coastal environments. The product will be used to holistically monitor and diagnose inland water characteristics and how these evolve at the river mouth when interacting with the marine environment. The resulting research and outreach tools also aim to support riverine and coastal monitoring activities (e.g. monitoring of living marine resources on delta environments) over</p>

	coastal zones that are particularly affected by river runoffs, i.e., nutrient inputs of terrestrial/anthropogenic origin.
Benefits for user/model/application	<p>FOCCUS User. The set of products will be useful for the assessment of water quality within riverine waters in estuary/delta environments. Potential users will be environmental agencies at national and regional (watershed) level, which could potentially take proactive measures to protect the coastal ecosystems and human health or diagnose past events in the light of other environmental stressors.</p> <p>FOCCUS Model. IOPs in riverine environments represent valuable datasets for land-ocean continuum model validation and, in general, for the assessment of biogeochemical tracers dispersion due to river plume dynamics. Eventually these products may serve for assimilation in order to improve predictability of water quality over lower branches of main rivers.</p> <p>FOCCUS Application. The set of products will contribute to the following FOCCUS applications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ESC 1 - Applications to better manage and protect the coastal area: pollution hazard/risk mapping by assessing the cumulative impacts of land based pollution and sediment resuspension. ● ESC 2 - Applications to enhance blue economy: support to multi-use coastal and off-shore operations, improving and integrating coastal observations and forecasting systems including biogeochemical processes. ● ESC 3 - Application related to natural and anthropogenic hazards. Assess natural hazards and extreme events by observing bio-optical effects of storm surges and coastal flooding using satellite.
KEY REFERENCES	
<p>Braga, F., Ciani, D., Colella, S., Organelli, E., Pitarch, J., Brando, V. E., ... & Falcini, F. (2022). COVID-19 lockdown effects on a coastal marine environment: Disentangling perception versus reality. <i>Science of the Total Environment</i>, 817, 153002.</p> <p>Dogliotti, A. I., Ruddick, K. G., Nechad, B., Doxaran, D., & Knaeps, E. (2015). A single algorithm to retrieve turbidity from remotely-sensed data in all coastal and estuarine waters. <i>Remote sensing of environment</i>, 156, 157-168.</p> <p>Pitarch, J., & Vanhellefont, Q. (2021). The QAA-RGB: A universal three-band absorption and backscattering retrieval algorithm for high resolution satellite sensors. <i>Development and implementation in ACOLITE. Remote Sensing of Environment</i>, 265, 112667.</p>	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.	

4.11. Sea level and currents

NAME OF THE VARIABLE

OVERVIEW: High-resolution sea level anomalies and currents induced by eddies emerging from SWOT data during the fast-sampling phase (April-July 2023) of the satellite mission. The detected eddies are then collocated with Argo profiling floats (temperature and salinity) and surface drifters to support Cal/Val activities. The wide-swath altimetry data used are the SWOT Level-4 products (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24400/527896/A01-2024.007>). First, mesoscale eddies are detected relying on geometrical and dynamical constraints based on the high resolution wide-swath altimetry sea-level anomaly and geostrophic current fields (Raj et al., 2016, 2020; Bonaduce et al., 2021). The eddy detection and tracking also allows for the collocation with in-situ autonomous profilers trapped by the eddies (Temperature, Salinity, Velocities). Once the detection, tracking and collocation with in-situ data are performed, the resulting data-set allows for the Cal/Val of SWOT retrievals. The data product based on the geographical positions, characteristics (size, polarity) of the eddies, as well as on their dynamical (surface elevation, ocean geostrophic currents), thermo-dynamical (temperature and salinity profiles) properties, and ocean total surface current (from surface drifters) are made available.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description
eddy_center_lon	Degrees East	Geographical position of the eddy centers
eddy_center_lat	Degrees North	Geographical position of the eddy centers
eddy_radius	km	Eddy radius
eddy_polarity	1/-1	Eddy polarity (anticyclones and cyclones)
eddy_sealevel_anomaly	cm	Sea-level anomalies associated to mesoscale eddies
eddy_zonal_velocity	m/s	Zonal eddy propagation velocity
eddy_meridional_velocity	m/s	Meridional eddy propagation velocity
temperature	degC	Temperature profiles from Argo floats trapped by eddies
salinity	PSU	Salinity profiles from Argo floats trapped by eddies
drifters_speed	m/s	Speed of drifters trapped by eddies

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description: The eddy detection algorithm consists of a hybrid detection based on both geometrical and dynamical constraints to identify the signatures of the same eddy over different variables (Raj et al., 2016; Cipollone et al., 2017; Bonaduce et al., 2021). The algorithm is

	further upgraded to include SWOT retrievals, and combine them with in-situ measurements. The first component is a geometric identification of local depression/elevation of sea surface that must be dominated by rotation or by streamlines with circular/spiral patterns (Chelton et al., 2011). The second component looks at the occurrence and persistence of a coherent rotation in the occurrence of each feature detected at the surface. The third component shapes the vertical structure of the eddy based on the vertical profiles of the Argo-profiling floats trapped by the eddies. The collocation with in-situ data also extends to surface drifters to extract the surface currents speed of mesoscale eddies.
Limitations:	Eddy detection algorithms rely on Level-4 products.
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES	
format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Sea-level and currents from altimetry and in-situ data"
summary	"High-resolution sea level anomalies and currents induced by eddies emerging from SWOT data during the fast-sampling phase (April-July 2023) of the satellite mission. The detected eddies are then collocated with Argo profiling floats (temperature and salinity) and surface drifters to support Cal/Val activities."
source_platform_category_code	"Satellite; drifting subsurface profiling floats"
platform	"SWOT"
platform_type	"low earth orbit satellite"
platform_vocabulary	"CEOS"
instrument	"Ka-band Radar Interferometer (KaRin)"
instrument_vocabulary	"CEOS"
band	"Ka"
institution	"Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center"
institution_edmo_code	"1413"
references	"Bonaduce, A., Cipollone, A., Johannessen, J. A., Staneva, J., Raj, R. P., and Aydogdu, A. (2021). Ocean Mesoscale Variability: A Case Study on the Mediterranean Sea From a Re-Analysis Perspective. Front. Earth Sci. 9. https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2021.724879 "
geospatial_lat_min	"60"
geospatial_lat_max	"78.5"
geospatial_lon_min	"-30.5"
geospatial_lon_max	"19"
geospatial_vertical_min	"0"
geospatial_vertical_max	"1000"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"irregular"
processing_level	"L4"
creator_name	"0000-0003-0191-1554", "0000-0001-5863-5269"
creator_url	"https://nersc.no"
contributor_name	"0000-0003-0191-1554", "0000-0001-5863-5269"

contributor_url	"https://nersc.no"
contributor_email	"post@nersc.no"
method	"Hybrid Eddy detection and collocation with in-situ autonomous measurements"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
USE CASES	
Overview	The dataset provides users with ocean surface elevations, currents, and vertical profiles induced by mesoscale variability in coastal and cross-shelf areas, allowing them to study the influence of ocean dynamics on thermodynamics and biology and their effect on ocean health.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User: NERSC, MET.no FOCCUS Model: TOPAZ, NorKyst800 FOCCUS Application: ECS1 - Management and protection of coastal areas. ESC3 - Storm surges, coastal flooding
KEY REFERENCES	
<p>Bonaduce, A., Cipollone, A., Johannessen, J. A., Staneva, J., Raj, R. P., and Aydogdu, A. (2021). Ocean Mesoscale Variability: A Case Study on the Mediterranean Sea From a Re-Analysis Perspective. <i>Front. Earth Sci.</i> 9. https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2021.724879</p> <p>Chelton, D. B., Schlax, M. G., and Samelson, R. M. (2011). Global observations of nonlinear mesoscale eddies. <i>Prog. Oceanogr.</i> 91, 167–216. doi: 10.1016/j.pocean.2011.01.002</p> <p>Cipollone, A., Masina, S., Storto, A., and Iovino, D. (2017). Benchmarking the mesoscale variability in global ocean eddy-permitting numerical systems. <i>Ocean Dyn.</i> 67, 1313–1333. doi: 10.1007/s10236-017-1089-5</p> <p>Raj, R. P., Halo, I., Chatterjee, S., Belonenko, T., Bakhoday-Paskyabi, M., Bashmachnikov, I., et al. (2020). Interaction Between Mesoscale Eddies and the Gyre Circulation in the Lofoten Basin. <i>J. Geophys. Res. Oceans</i> 125, e2020JC016102. doi: 10.1029/2020JC016102</p> <p>Raj, R. P., Johannessen, J. A., Eldevik, T., Nilsen, J. E. Ø., and Halo, I. (2016). Quantifying mesoscale eddies in the Lofoten Basin. <i>J. Geophys. Res. Oceans</i> 121, 4503–4521. doi: 10.1002/2016JC011637</p>	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025	

4.12. FRM for ocean color and sea surface temperature radiometer observations

4.12.1 In-situ radiometric measurements for ocean colour in riverine water

In-situ radiometric measurements for ocean colour in riverine water

OVERVIEW: Water reflectance in the spectral range of 400-900 nm derived from autonomous in-situ hyperspectral radiometric measurements at a fixed position in the Po river. Water reflectance is derived from irradiance and radiance measured by an above water radiometer system (WISPstation - Water Insight), enabling continuous and autonomous measurements for water quality monitoring and Ocean Colour satellite validation. A quality check and the correction for observation geometry (sunglint and skylint) are performed and then weekly spectra are provided.

An automatic in-situ hyperspectral sensor has the advantages of non-contact and low maintenance costs (excluding sensor calibration), but it is easily affected by changes in lighting conditions and cannot operate at night.

The WISPstation was installed on 11th September 2024 at Pontelagoscuro station.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description
In-situ Rrs	sr ⁻¹	in-situ Remote sensing reflectance

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:

The WISPstation provides above water remote sensing reflectance (Rrs) measurements, derived from 2 sets of sky radiance (L_{sky}), upwelling radiance (L_{up}) and downwelling irradiance (E_d). The viewing geometry of the system is based on Mobley (1999), namely azimuth angle is optimal around 138 degrees from the sun, L_{up} angle is around 42 degrees from the nadir and L_{sky} angle is around 42 degrees from the zenith. Using the two sets of sensors looking in two directions (modification of Wernand (2022)), the instrument provides two optimal viewing geometry moments during the day and a large time window with acceptable viewing geometries that can be accounted for.

At Pontelagoscuro (Po river), WISPstation was installed looking in a NNW direction, which is not the optimal viewing geometry, but it permits a free view of the water surface and an absence of obstacles above the instrument.

Rrs measured using the above water approach usually are affected by reflected skylight from the water surface, which largely influences the accuracy. Therefore, correction and removal of the residual reflected skylight for Rrs measured from above-water approach is necessary before using it for algorithm development and satellite product validation. We

	will test different methods to remove the residual reflected skylight from above-water measured Rrs, i.e. Jiang et al. (2020) and Pitarch et al. (2020).
Limitations:	An internal Quality Control is available, but further analyses are necessary to identify and flag sub-optimal measurements (affected by sun and skylint, low illumination conditions, floating materials, etc.). Sun and skylint corrections are under development, considering the highly varying water types and environmental conditions, mainly influenced by water discharge (between flood and drought).
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
format version	"v1.0"
title	"In-situ radiometric measurements for Ocean Colour in the Po river"
summary	"The dataset includes a time series of water reflectance spectra, averaged on weekly bases, in the spectral range of 400-900 nm"
source_platform_category_code	"land platform; river station"
platform	"river station"
platform_type	"river station"
platform_vocabulary	"BODC"
instrument	"WISPStation"
instrument_vocabulary	"_"
institution	"CNR-ISMAR"
institution_edmo_code	"227"
references	-
product_version	"1.0"
comment	"weekly above water radiometry"
area	"Po river; Adriatic Sea"
cdm_data_type	"timeseries"
geospatial_lat_min	44.88°
geospatial_lat_max	44.88°
geospatial_lon_min	11.61°
geospatial_lon_max	11.61°
gesopatial_vertical_min	0
geospatial_vertical_max	0
geospatial_vertical_positive	0
geospatial_vertical_resolution	0
grid_resolution	0
update_interval	P1M
processing_level	"v1.0"
creator_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3562-7180 https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5061-5607
creator_url	-
contributor_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3562-7180

	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5061-5607
method	-
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	gsk@artov.ismar.cnr.it
technical_support_contact	gsk@artov.ismar.cnr.it
USE CASES	
Overview	This dataset can be used for OC satellite data validation, providing weekly spectra of Rrs.
Benefits for user/model/application	<p>FOCCUS User. CNR, TBD.</p> <p>FOCCUS Model. NA</p> <p>FOCCUS Application. Match ups for OC satellite data, with the potential to derive additional parameters as Water turbidity and IOP from spectra for FOCCUS activities (i.e., Inland-marine water connectivity, BGC anomalies and trends).</p>
KEY REFERENCES	
<p>Jiang, D., Matsushita, B., & Yang, W. (2020). A simple and effective method for removing residual reflected skylight in above-water remote sensing reflectance measurements. <i>ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing</i>, 165, 16-27.</p> <p>Mobley, C. D. (1999). Estimation of the remote-sensing reflectance from above-surface measurements. <i>Applied optics</i>, 38(36), 7442-7455.</p> <p>Pitarch, J., Talone, M., Zibordi, G., & Groetsch, P. (2020). Determination of the remote-sensing reflectance from above-water measurements with the “3C model”: a further assessment. <i>Optics Express</i>, 28(11), 15885-15906.</p> <p>Wernand, M. R. (2002, November). Guidelines for (ship-borne) auto-monitoring of coastal and ocean colour. In <i>Proceedings of Ocean Optics XVI (Vol. 13)</i>.</p>	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.	

4.12.2 FRM for sea surface temperature radiometer observations

SST FRM

OVERVIEW: The fiducial reference measurements collected by the Infrared Scanning Autonomous Radiometer (ISAR) from ships of opportunity have provided high-precision SST data essential for validating satellite-based observations. ISAR autonomously records SST variations with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, and is traceable to SI standards with pre- and post deployment calibration procedures. The data collected by DMI offer longitudinal transects across the North Sea as ships travel through the region. These measurements serve as ground-truth reference observations, crucial for calibrating satellite algorithms and improving climate models. Currently DMI ISAR measurements have been collected mostly in the North Sea, however there is the capacity to extend this to

	areas in the Baltic. Similarly, numerous buoys and ARGO floats are operational in both the Baltic and North Sea, offering further metrics for the validation of satellite algorithms.	
MAIN VARIABLES		
Name	Units (SI)	Description
sea_surface_temperature	kelvin	native sea surface temperature
sst_total_uncertainty	Kelvin	Total uncertainty (systematic and random) associated with each SST measurement.
SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY		
Algorithm description:	The ISAR algorithm converts infrared measurements into accurate SST using radiative transfer theory (e.g. infrared radiation emitted from the sea surface) and correcting for reflected sky radiation, atmospheric conditions and sensor calibration drift. Recent improvements focus on refining atmospheric corrections and reducing errors from varying sensor angles, enhancing the reliability of SST data for satellite validation and climate research.	
Limitations:	ISAR's accuracy can be affected by extreme weather/waves, limiting optimal performance due to roll and spray. Its spatial coverage is restricted to ship routes, and data collection is intermittent when ships are not in operation.	
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)		
format_version	"v0.1"	
title	"SST FRM observations from ISAR on ships of opportunity"	
summary	The ISAR measures the infrared emission from the sea surface and atmosphere in the spectral waveband 9.8-11 μm using a Heitronics KT15 radiometer. The ISAR system has been specifically designed to address the problem of sea-water spray or rain, which without adequate environmental protection of delicate infrared radiometer fore-optics, could introduce significant errors in the skin SST measurement. Furthermore it provides a self-calibrating infrared radiometer system with two internal blackbody reference targets that are visited at every observation cycle (~3-4 minutes).	
source_platform_category_code	"Ships of opportunity"	
platform	"Ship's underway"	
platform_type	"research vessel"	
platform_vocabulary	"BODC"	
instrument	ISAR narrow band sensor (9.6 - 11.5 microns, view angle ~12 degrees), developed at NOCS.	
instrument_vocabulary	"BODC"	
institution	"Danish Meteorological Institute"	
institution_edmo_code	469	
references	Gacitúa, G., Høyer, J. L., Søjbjerg, S. S., Shi, H., Skarpalezos, S., Karagali, I., ... & Donlon, C. (2024). Shipborne Comparison of Infrared and Passive Microwave Radiometers for Sea Surface Temperature Observations. EGU sphere, 2024, 1-28. Donlon, C., Robinson, I. S., Wimmer, W., Fisher, G., Reynolds, M.,	

	Edwards, R., & Nightingale, T. J. (2008). An infrared sea surface temperature autonomous radiometer (ISAR) for deployment aboard voluntary observing ships (VOS). <i>Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology</i> , 25(1), 93-113.
product_version	"1.0"
comment	ISAR FRM SST
area	North Sea
cdm_data_type	grid
geospatial_lat_min	55
geospatial_lat_max	62
geospatial_lon_min	-18
geospatial_lon_max	8.3
geospatial_vertical_min	-15
geospatial_vertical_max	2
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	NA
grid_resolution	"1 m"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"_"
creator_name	Danish Meteorological Institute
creator_url	"www.dmi.dk"
contributor_name	0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924
method	"in-situ measurements, quality control, gridding, and interpolation"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	"algh@dmi.dk"
technical_support_contact	"algh@dmi.dk"
USE CASES	
Overview	The SST FRM data collected by ISAR in the North Sea, coastal Denmark, Iceland, and the Faroe Islands provides accurate sea surface temperature measurements essential for multiple applications. These measurements enhance oceanographic models, enabling better predictions of local ocean conditions, which benefits forecasting in these regions. By tracking long-term temperature trends, the data supports climate change research, while serving as an in-situ reference for satellite SST measurements, ensuring accurate, reliable environmental monitoring for diverse stakeholders.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS USER: DMI, CNR FOCCUS Model: FOCCUS Application: Coastal Match ups for SST observations with satellite data, with the potential to de-flag coastal sites, understand accuracy of satellite retrievals, and how this changes with distance to coast.

KEY REFERENCES

Donlon, C., Robinson, I. S., Wimmer, W., Fisher, G., Reynolds, M., Edwards, R., & Nightingale, T. J. (2008). An infrared sea surface temperature autonomous radiometer (ISAR) for deployment aboard volunteer observing ships (VOS). *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 25(1), 93-113.

Gacitúa, G., Høyer, J. L., Søbjaerg, S. S., Shi, H., Skarpalezos, S., Karagali, I., ... & Donlon, C. (2024). Shipborne Comparison of Infrared and Passive Microwave Radiometers for Sea Surface Temperature Observations. *EGUsphere*, 2024, 1-28.

Ships4SST. (n.d.). Ships4SST data services. Retrieved December 9, 2024, from <https://ships4sst.org/services/ships4sst-data>

HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?

The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025

4.13. Beach morphodynamic processes

4.13.1 Beach-imaging AI-derived shorelines

SHORELINE POSITION

OVERVIEW: Image-derived shorelines from land-based remote sensing systems (i.e. fixed beach imaging stations) leveraging deep learning segmentation approaches. The dataset provides a time series of multipoint geometries (xyz) in a shapefile. Each row or feature in the shapefile represents the shoreline at a specific time and location, including beaches in the Balearic Islands, the Romanian coast, and the Cascais beach (Portugal).

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description (long name)
LAT (Mandatory)	degree_north	Latitude is positive northward (latitude)
LON (Mandatory)	degree_east	Longitude is positive eastward (longitude)
TIME (Mandatory)	days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00Z	Time measured in days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC using the gregorian calendar (time)
ALT (Mandatory)	m	The -geometric- height above the geoid, which is the reference geopotential surface (altitude above the geoid)
SHRL_ID (Mandatory)	1	Proxy to represent the shoreline position (shoreline proxy)
PLTF_ID (Mandatory)	1	Identifies the platform from which an observation was made (platform_id)
PLTF_N (Mandatory)	1	Station description such as the geographical place (platform_name).
QC (Mandatory)	1	Indicator of assessed quality information of positioning (quality flag).
Other optional variables	Report T2.3.1 (section 4.1.1)	

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	Instantaneous waterline position is derived from land-based imaging systems. Oblique images from each site are spatially coregistered, and rectified (projected to a terrain coordinate system) using photogrammetric algorithms. Shorelines are automatically extracted from the resulting planview using DL segmentation approaches. All shorelines undergo non-interactive quality control.
Limitations:	Shoreline positions are delivered at irregular intervals across various sites. Shoreline points are not equidistant across all sites and timestamps. Additionally, the positioning accuracy of image-derived shoreline points may degrade with increasing distance to the camera.
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:	
format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Instantaneous shoreline position data from land-based beach imaging systems"
summary	The dataset includes a times series of instantaneous shoreline positions at Cala Millor beach. The instantaneous shoreline is the position of the waterline (swash uprush limit) at one instant in time derived from rectified beach images using DL segmentation approaches
source_platform_category_code	"land/onshore structure; human"
platform	"building; human"
platform_type	"land/onshore structure; human"
platform_vocabulary	"BODC"
instrument	"DFK 41AF02 Color Camera; Leica GS10 RTK-GNSS; GEOMAX Zenith60 RTK-GNSS"
instrument_vocabulary	"BODC"
institution	"Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System"
institution_edmo_code	"3410"
references	"_"
product_version	"1.0"
version_date	"YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"
comment	The Cala Millor beach video-monitoring system consists of 5 RGB cameras mounted at the top of a building (elevation ~ 47 m) at the beachfront. Cameras take oblique pictures of the beach (1280x960 px) with overlapping sights. Images are rectified to a terrain coordinate system using photogrammetric algorithms, and the shoreline is automatically extracted using DL segmentation methods. Detailed information regarding the data set's development, accuracy metrics, and the quality control performed can be found in the data set.
geospatial_lat_min	39.5891481005203687

geospatial_lat_max	39.6018117647248360
geospatial_lon_min	3.3842558134392791
geospatial_lon_max	3.3866966557462623
geospatial_vertical_min	-
geospatial_vertical_max	-
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"1 m"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"L3"
creator_name	0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924
creator_url	"https://socib.es"
contributor_name	0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924
method	"image processing (photogrammetry), DL-based shoreline extraction, accuracy (validation), quality control "
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	"mobims@socib.es"
technical_support_contact	"datacenter@socib.es"

USE CASES

Overview	The shoreline position serves as an integrated and fundamental proxy in the fields of coastal research, engineering, and management. The dataset allows the user to study the spatiotemporal dynamics of beach behaviour, and the erosion and accretion trends at different time scales, their impact in coastal evolution, and has applications in cal/val exercises related to satellite-derived shorelines.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User - SOCIB, +ATLANTIC FOCCUS Application - Coastal erosion, Combating degradation of ecosystems, Storm surges, coastal flooding

KEY REFERENCES

Fernández-Mora, À., Criado, F. F., Gómez, L., Tintoré, J., Orfila, A. (2023). Ten years of morphodynamic data at a micro-tidal urban beach: Cala Millor (Western Mediterranean Sea). *Scientific Data*, 10(301). 10.1038/s41597-023-02210-2.

González-Villanueva, R., Sánchez, E., Soriano, J. (2023). SCShores: time-series of shorelines from Spanish Sandy beaches from citizen-science monitoring program [Dataset]. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.8056415.

Martí-Puig, P., Serra-Serra, M., Ribas, F., Simarro, G., Caballeria, M. (2024). Automatic shoreline detection by processing planview timex images using bi-LSTM networks, *Expert Systems with Applications*, 240, 122566.

Soriano, J., González-Villanueva, R., & Sánchez, E. (2023). SCLabels: Labelled rectified RGB images from the Spanish CoastSnap network [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/10159978>.

HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?

The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025

4.13.2 Satellite-derived shorelines

SHORELINE POSITION

OVERVIEW: Satellite-derived shorelines from Sentinel-2 and PlanetScope leveraging deep learning segmentation approaches and subpixel refinement methods. The dataset provides a time series of multipoint geometries in a shapefile. Each row or feature in the shapefile represents the shoreline at a specific time and location, including beaches in the Balearic Islands (Spain), Romania, and Portugal.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description (long name)
LAT (Mandatory)	degree_north	Latitude is positive northward (latitude)
LON (Mandatory)	degree_east	Longitude is positive eastward (longitude)
TIME (Mandatory)	days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00Z	Time measured in days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC using the gregorian calendar (time)
SHRL_ID (Mandatory)	1	Proxy to represent the shoreline position (shoreline proxy)
PLTF_ID (Mandatory)	1	Identifies the platform from which an observation was made (platform_id)
PLTF_N (Mandatory)	1	Station description such as the geographical place (platform_name).
QC (Mandatory)	1	Indicator of assessed quality information of positioning (quality flag).

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	The most probable shoreline at the best satellite resolution (pixel size) is derived using a segmentation approach that relies on a DL model trained for the specific task and platform. Then, different processing methods are applied to achieve subpixel precision (e.g., marching squares, neighbourhood spectral analyses).
Limitations:	Shoreline positions are delivered at irregular intervals across various sites. Shoreline points are not equidistant across all sites and timestamps.

METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)

GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:

format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Instantaneous shoreline position data from optical remote sensing platforms"
summary	The dataset includes a time series of instantaneous shoreline positions at beaches in the Balearic Islands (Spain), Romania, and Portugal. The instantaneous shoreline is the position of the waterline (swash uprush

	limit) at one instant in time, derived from optical remote sensing platforms.
source_platform_category_code	"satellite"
platform	"Sentinel-2"
platform_type	"orbiting satellite"
platform_vocabulary	"BODC"
instrument	"MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI)"
instrument_vocabulary	"BODC"
institution	"Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System"
institution_edmo_code	"3410"
references	
product_version	"1.0"
version_date	"YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"
comment	Detailed information regarding the data set's development, accuracy metrics, and the quality control performed can be found in the data set.
geospatial_lat_min	39.588189
geospatial_lat_max	39.603741
geospatial_lon_min	3.3842558134392791
geospatial_lon_max	3.3866966557462623
geospatial_vertical_min	-
geospatial_vertical_max	-
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"1 m"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"L3"
creator_name	"0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924"
creator_url	"https://socib.es"
contributor_name	"0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924"
method	"Sentinel-2 L1C subset and DL-based segmentation, subpixel extraction, accuracy (validation), quality control "
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	"mobims@socib.es"
technical_support_contact	"datacenter@socib.es"
USE CASES	
Overview	The shoreline position serves as an integrated and fundamental proxy in the fields of coastal research, engineering, and management. The dataset allows the user to study the spatiotemporal dynamics of beach behaviour, and the erosion and accretion trends at different time scales, and their impact in coastal evolution.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User - SOCIB, +ATLANTIC, MHD FOCCUS Model - GCOAST-BS FOCCUS Application - Coastal erosion, Combating degradation of ecosystems, Storm surges, coastal flooding

KEY REFERENCES

Buscombe, D., Goldstein, E., Sherwood, C., Bodine, C., Brown, J., Favela, J., et al. (2021). Human-in-the-Loop segmentation of Earth surface imagery. *Earth and Space Science*, 9(3), e2021EA002085.

Buscombe, D., & Goldstein, E. B. (2022). A reproducible and reusable pipeline for segmentation of geoscientific imagery. *Earth and Space Science*, 9, e2022EA002332.

Palomar-Vázquez, J., Pardo-Pascual, J. E., Almonacid-Caballer, J., & Cabezas-Rabadán, C. (2023). Shoreline Analysis and Extraction Tool (SAET): A New Tool for the Automatic Extraction of Satellite-Derived Shorelines with Subpixel Accuracy. *Remote Sensing*, 15(12), 3198.

Vos, K., Splinter, K., Harley, M., Simmons, J., Turner, I., 2019. CoastSat: A Google Earth Engine-enabled Python toolkit to extract shorelines from publicly available satellite imagery. *Environ. Model. Softw.*, 122, 104528.

HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?

The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025.

4.13.3 Beach-imaging derived beach wracks

BEACH WRACKS POSITION

OVERVIEW: Approximate beach seagrass wracks coverage in 2 Balearic Islands beaches derived from beach video-monitoring systems imagery. The resulting products are grids (5 m spatial resolution) with information on the area fraction occupied by beach seagrass wracks in each cell. Products are delivered in the form of time series (NetCDF) in separate files for each beach.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description (long name)
LAT (Mandatory)	degree_north	Latitude is positive northward (latitude)
LON (Mandatory)	degree_east	Longitude is positive eastward (longitude)
TIME (Mandatory)	days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00Z	Time measured as days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC using the gregorian calendar (time)
COVR (Mandatory)	1	The fraction of a grid cell's horizontal area that has beach seagrass wracks. It is evaluated as the area of beach seagrass wracks divided by the grid cell area (area_fraction)

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description: Images are processed using deep learning detection and segmentation techniques to automatically identify beach wracks. Photogrammetric algorithms are then employed to determine the approximate location and coverage of the beach wracks.

Limitations: The quality of images in time series can be affected by various factors, such as weather constraints, which can lead to irregular

	data. Meteorological and external factors can cause camera displacements, compromising the accuracy of beach seagrass wrack geolocation. Additionally, the coverage accuracy of pixels located further away from the camera may be lower.
METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)	
GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:	
format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Beach seagrass wrack coverage at Cala Millor beach from beach videomonitoring images"
summary	The dataset includes a time series of beach wracks coverage at the Cala Millor beach gridded at 5 m spatial resolution.
source_platform_category_code	"land/onshore structure"
platform	"building"
platform_type	"land/onshore structure"
platform_vocabulary	"BODC"
instrument	"DFK 41AF02 Color Camera"
instrument_vocabulary	"BODC"
institution	"Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System"
institution_edmo_code	"3410"
references	-
product_version	"1.0"
version_date	"YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"
comment	The Cala Millor beach video-monitoring system consists of 5 RGB cameras mounted at the top of a building (elevation ~ 47 m) at the beachfront. Cameras take oblique pictures of the beach (1280x960 px) with overlapping sights. Using object detection and segmentation deep learning models, beach seagrass wracks are identified in oblique images. Then, images are rectified to a terrain coordinate system using photogrammetric algorithms, and beach seagrass wracks coverage, represented as the area fraction per cell, is set over a 5 m grid. Detailed information regarding the data set's development and the quality control performed can be found in the data set documentation.
geospatial_lat_min	39.5891481005203687
geospatial_lat_max	39.6018117647248360
geospatial_lon_min	3.3842558134392791
geospatial_lon_max	3.3866966557462623
geospatial_vertical_min	-
geospatial_vertical_max	-
geospatial_vertical_positive	"up"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"1 m"
grid_resolution	"5 m"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"L4"
creator_name	"0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X;

	0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924”
creator_url	“https://socib.es”
contributor_name	“0000-0003-0150-1432; 0000-0002-4724-362X; 0000-0002-8642-2436; 0000-0001-6573-3924”
method	“Object detection and segmentation (deep learning), image coordinate transformation (photogrammetry), quality control (automatic)”
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	“mobims@socib.es”
technical_support_contact	“datacenter@socib.es”
USE CASES	
Overview	The dataset allows the user to study the spatiotemporal dynamics of beach seagrass wracks, unveiling their formation and dismantling processes and their impact in coastal evolution. It has applications in coastal research and beach management.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User - SOCIB FOCCUS Model - N/A FOCCUS Application - Coastal erosion, Combating degradation of ecosystems
KEY REFERENCES	
<p>Gómez-Pujol, L., Orfila, A., Álvarez-Ellacuría, A., Terrados, J., Tintoré, J. 2013. Posidonia oceanica beach-cast litter in Mediterranean beaches: a coastal videomonitoring study. <i>Journal of Coastal Research</i>, 65, 1768-1773.</p> <p>Gómez-Pujol, L., Zamora, A., Fernández-Mora, À., Souto, P., Orfila, A. 2019. Seagrass berm accumulation and dismantling on microtidal Mediterranean beaches: a 7-year record. In <i>EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts</i> (p. 18993).</p> <p>Nieto, M.A., Garau, B., Balle, S., Simarro, G., Zarruk, G.A., Ortiz, A., Tintoré, J., Álvarez-Ellacuría, A., Gómez-Pujol, L. and Orfila, A. 2010. An open source, low cost video-based coastal monitoring system. <i>Earth Surf. Process. Landforms</i>, 35, 1712-1719.</p> <p>Soriano-González, J., Sánchez-García, E., Oliver-Sansó, J., Pérez-Cañellas, J. D., Criado-Sudau, F., Gómez-Pujol, L., & Fernández-Mora, À. (2024). <i>BWILD: Beach seagrass Wrack Identification Labelled Dataset (1.0.0)</i> [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12698764</p>	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025	

4.13.4 Satellite-derived bathymetry

SATELLITE DERIVED BATHYMETRY

OVERVIEW: Satellite imagery from Sentinel-2 and PlanetScope multispectral sensors is used to predict bathymetry values (depth of the seafloor below the sea surface when the satellite image was taken) for shallow waters (depth from 0 - 12 m). Shallow water bathymetry (SWB) data offers valuable insights into beach morphodynamics, identifying areas of deposition and erosion, and is essential for applications like climate change adaptation, flood risk assessment, dredging, marine planning, and coastal management. Satellite-derived bathymetry provides an efficient means of monitoring these dynamics, supporting stakeholders like coastal authorities, hydrographic institutes, ports, and researchers in understanding and managing sediment and coastal resources in a cost effective way.

MAIN VARIABLES

Name	Units (SI)	Description
BATH (Mandatory)	metre	Vertical distance between the sea surface and the seabed as measured at a given point in space including the variance caused by tides and possibly waves (bathymetric depth)
LAT (Mandatory)	degree_north	Latitude is positive northward (latitude)
LON (Mandatory)	degree_east	Longitude is positive eastward (longitude)
TIME (Mandatory)	days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00Z	Time measured as days since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC using the gregorian calendar (time)
PLTF_ID (Mandatory)	1	Identifies the platform from which an observation was made (platform_id)
PLTF_N (Mandatory)	1	Station description such as the geographical place (platform_name).
QC (Mandatory)	1	Indicator of assessed quality information of positioning (quality flag).

SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY

Algorithm description:	Region-specific Machine Learning models, such as Random Forest, XGBoost, and Artificial Neural Networks, are trained using surface reflectance bands from atmospherically corrected satellite images along with high-resolution bathymetric and in-situ data. Bathymetry estimations are then generated on new satellite imagery.
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Limitations:	<p>The bathymetric information only covers shallow water regions. The surface reflectance values across wavelength bands vary significantly with seabed substrate, water column properties, and surface roughness, making each model region-specific. Additionally, model training requires in-situ bathymetry data from the specific areas of interest.</p> <p>The data is provided without any warranty, either explicit or implied, including warranties of merchantability or fitness for a specific purpose. The data should not be used for navigation or any purpose relating to safety at sea.</p>
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METADATA INFORMATION (Specific global attributes)

GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES

format_version	"v0.1"
title	"Satellite derived bathymetry in Costa da Caparica"
summary	The dataset includes a time series of satellite-derived shallow water bathymetry (depth of the seafloor below the sea surface) in Costa da Caparica coastal region.
source_platform_category_code	"satellite"
platform	"Sentinel-2"
platform_type	"orbiting satellite"
platform_vocabulary	"BODC"
instrument	"MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI)"
instrument_vocabulary	"BODC"
institution	"CoLAB +ATLANTIC"
institution_edmo_code	"5952"
references	-
product_version	"1.0"
version_date	"YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"
geospatial_lat_min	38.629168
geospatial_lat_max	38.665366
geospatial_lon_min	-9.271645
geospatial_lon_max	-9.231042
geospatial_vertical_min	12
geospatial_vertical_max	0
geospatial_vertical_positive	"down"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	"1 m"
grid_resolution	"10 m"
update_interval	"void"
processing_level	"L4"
creator_name	https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0157-2202
creator_url	" https://colabatlantic.com/ "

contributor_name	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7805-9086
method	"Atmospheric correction, DL-based segmentation and regression, ML-driven gap filling, quality control"
track_id	Will be available in D2.2
scientific_support_contact	" luis.figueiredo@colabatlantic.com "
technical_support_contact	" atlanticsense@colabatlantic.com "
USE CASES	
Overview	Generate a time series of satellite-derived bathymetry predictions for the Costa da Caparica beach using a Machine Learning model. Frequent sand nourishment interventions are carried out in this region to counteract significant erosion and expand the beach area. By analysing these bathymetry predictions over time, we hope to identify sediment movement patterns, gain insights into where sand is dispersing, and potentially pinpoint optimal locations for future nourishment efforts. This approach could improve the effectiveness of interventions and support sustainable beach management.
Benefits for user/model/application	FOCCUS User - +CoLAB +ATLANTIC, SOCIB FOCCUS Model - N/A FOCCUS Application - Coastal erosion, modelling coastal overtopping and flooding.
KEY REFERENCES	
<p>Ashphaq, M., Srivastava, P.K.,Mitra, D. 2021. Review of near-shore satellite derived bathymetry: Classification and account of five decades of coastal bathymetry research. <i>Journal of Ocean Engineering and Science</i>, 6(4), 340-359.</p> <p>Bio, A., Gonçalves, J.A., Magalhães, A., Pinheiro, J., Bastos, L. 2020. Combining Low-Cost Sonar and High-Precision Global Navigation Satellite System for Shallow Water Bathymetry. <i>Estuaries Coast</i>, 45, 1000–1011.</p> <p>Mandlbürger, G., Kölle, M., Nübel, H., Soergel, U., 2021. BathyNet: A deep neural network for water depth mapping from multispectral aerial images. <i>PFG–Journal of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Geoinformation Science</i>, 89(2), 71-89.</p> <p>Poursanidis, D., Traganos, D., Reinartz, P., Chrysoulakis, N., 2019. On the use of Sentinel-2 for coastal habitat mapping and satellite-derived bathymetry estimation using downscaled coastal aerosol band. <i>International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation</i>, 80, 58-70.</p>	
HOW TO ACCESS AND CITE THIS DATA PRODUCT?	
The DOI for this data product will be available in the "First version of data or development" deliverable (D2.2), scheduled for publication on February 28th, 2025	

Annex I: List of mandatory and recommended metadata for the data products

This Annex defines **metadata standards and naming conventions for NetCDF files** generated within FOCCUS WP2/3 to ensure consistency, facilitate data discovery, and promote interoperability. These standards, based on the OceanSITES manual (2014)⁷ and the [FOCCUS Data Management Plan](#), specify mandatory **M** and recommended **R** metadata elements.

Common metadata (i.e. global attributes) to all data products (e.g. time-related variables) are highlighted (**bold faced**) in the table below. Specific metadata for each product are detailed in [section 4](#). BODC, EMODnet and CMEMS collaboration improved metadata, ensuring discoverability of new data products.

Key metadata include:

- **Identification:** Title, publication details, project information (name, acronym, number), and licensing.
- **Location:** Spatial and temporal coverage (using WGS84 and ISO 8601 standards), and depth (according to the ISO-19115).
- **Data characteristics:** Source, keywords (GCMD vocabulary), parameters, units (CMEMS conventions), and quality control information.

Additional guidelines:

- Remove **creator names** and nominative emails unless requested: ORCID and institutional emails are recommended, instead.
- Use **SeaDataNet vocabularies** for [platforms](#) and [sensors](#).
- Supported file **formats** include **NetCDF, Zarr, GeoTIFF, and Shapefile**.

VARIABLE NAMES			
https://archimer.ifremer.fr/doc/00422/53381/			
DIMENSIONS:			
<i>They provide information on the size of the data variables and additionally tie coordinate variables to data.</i>			
Name	Description	M/R	Example
TIME	Number of time steps.	M	TIME=unlimited
DEPTH	Number of depth levels	M	DEPTH=5
LATITUDE	Dimension of the LATITUDE coordinate variable	M	LATITUDE=1
LONGITUDE	Dimension of the LONGITUDE coordinate variable	M	LONGITUDE=1

⁷ OceanSITES data management team (2014). OceanSITES Data Format Reference Manual. NetCDF Conventions and Reference Tables. Ifremer. <https://doi.org/10.13155/36149>

GLOBAL ATTRIBUTES:			
Name	Description	M/R	Example
Conventions used			
format_version	Version of the data model release.	M	"v0.1"
Conventions	A comma-separated list of the conventions that are followed by the dataset. Use: Standard name vocabulary , OceanSITES Manual , Copernicus In Situ TAC Parameters List , GCMD Science keywords , ISO 8601 date and time format	M	"CF-1.11, ACDD-1.3, ISO 8601, WGS84, GCMD, CopernicusInSituTAC-ParametersList-3.3.0, OceanSITES-Manual-1.3, CF-Standard-Names"
netcdf_version	NetCDF version used for the dataset	R	"4.1.3"
netcdf_format	NetCDF format used for the dataset	R	"netcdf4_classic"
Discovery and identification			
title	Free-format short text describing the dataset.	M	"High-Resolution Total Surface Currents"
summary	Longer-free format text describing the dataset (max. 100 words)	M	"High-resolution ocean surface current velocity product derived from Sentinel-1 SAR data. Covers 250 km swath with 1 km pixel size along the Norwegian coast. Uses a two-step algorithm: recalibration of satellite pointing errors and removal of sea-state signal. Final products are geospatial grids with velocity and direction fields."
project	EDMERP of the scientific project that produced the data.	M	13800
source_platform_category_code	Platform categories, as a code and label. Use: L06 (SeaVoX Platform Categories) . Use the preferred label and URI.	M	"coastal structure": http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/17/
phase	Use: Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7 , Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3 already used in ESA projects. It is very specific for SAR satellites.	M	"operational"
platform	Name of the platform(s) that supported the sensor data used to create this data set or product.	M	"Sentinel-1 A"

	<p>Platforms can be of any type, including satellite, ship, station, aircraft or other. Indicate controlled vocabulary used in platform_vocabulary.</p> <p>Use: SeaDataNet vocabularies for platforms (L06 SeaVoX Platform Categories). Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7, Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3 already used in ESA projects</p>		
platform_type	<p>Use: a term from L06 SeaVoX Platform Categories, Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7, Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3 already used in ESA projects</p>	M	"low earth orbit satellite"
platform_vocabulary	<p>Controlled vocabulary for names used in the "platform" attribute.</p> <p>Use: Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7, Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3 already used in ESA projects</p>	M	<p>"Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/data/tools/idn/ceos-mim-keywords/"; "British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/vocabularies/"; "NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/"; "NASA's Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) https://gcmd.earthdata.nasa.gov/KeywordViewer/scheme/all?gtm_scheme=all" (for satellite instances in general)</p>
instrument	<p>Name of the contributing instrument(s) or sensor(s) used to create this data set or product. Indicate controlled vocabulary used in instrument_vocabulary.</p> <p>Use: SeaDataNet vocabularies for sensors L22 (SeaVoX Device Catalogue). Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7, Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3 already used in ESA projects</p>	M	"C-Band SAR"
instrument_vocabulary	<p>Controlled vocabulary for the names used in the "instrument" attribute.</p> <p>Use: Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7, Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3</p>	M	"NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS)"; "CEOS"

	already used in ESA projects		
band	Use: Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7, Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3 already used in ESA projects	M	"C"
polarization	Use: Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7, Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3 already used in ESA projects	M	"VV"
radar_wavenumber	Use: Climate and Forecast (CF) 1.7, Attribute Convention for Data Discovery (ACDD) 1.3 already used in ESA projects	M	"113.28034"
institution	Specifies institution where the original data was produced	M	"Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center"
institution_edmo_code	Specifies institution EDMO codes managed by SeaDataNet project. Use: https://edmo.seadatanet.org/search , list of EDMO codes for FOCCUS partners	M	"3410"
references	Published or web-based references that describe the data or methods used to produce. Recommend URIs (such as a URL or DOI) for papers or other references. This attribute is defined in the CF conventions.	M	"Moiseev, A., Johnsen, H., Johannessen, J. A., Collard, F., & Guitton, G. (2020). On removal of sea state contribution to Sentinel-1 Doppler shift for retrieving Reliable Ocean surface current. Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans, 125, e2020JC016288. https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JC016288 "
product_version	Version of the data product	R	"1.0"
version_date	The date the data file was last modified. Use:ISO8601 standard:"YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"	M	"2024-09-17T00:30:00Z"
keywords	Provide comma-separated list of terms that will aid in discovery of the dataset. Use: GCMD Science keywords	M	"FOCCUS; Copernicus; Coastal; Ocean; In Situ". Additional ones that might be considered: Earth Science; Ocean Circulation; Ocean Currents"
keywords_vocabulary	Please use GCMD Science keywords.	M	"NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Science Keywords"
comment	Free-text providing miscellaneous information about the data or methods used to produce it.	R	"The product utilizes a two-step algorithm: re-calibration of satellite pointing errors and removal of sea-state-induced signals."

Geo-spatial-temporal			
area	Geographical coverage. Use: SeaVoX salt and fresh water body gazetteer (C19).	R	"North Sea"; "Mediterranean Sea"; "North Atlantic";...
cdm_data_type	The Unidata CDM (common data model) data type used by THREDDS Use: https://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/cf-conventions.html#_features_and_feature_types	R	"swath"; "point"; "timeSeries"; "trajectory"; "profile"; "timeSeriesProfile"; "trajectoryProfile"
time_coverage_start	Data start date in UTC. Time must be defined as a string according to ISO8601 standard: "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"	M	"2024-09-17T00:30:00Z"
time_coverage_end	Final data date in UTC. Time must be defined as a string according to ISO8601 standard: "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"	M	"2024-09-19T00:30:00Z"
time_coverage_resolution	Interval between records. Use: ISO8691 standard PnYnMnDTnHnMnS .	R	PT1H
time_coverage_duration	Duration of the time coverage of the data. Use: ISO8691 standard PnYnMnDTnHnMnS .	R	PT1H
geospatial_lat_min	The southernmost latitude, a value between -90 and 90 degrees.	M	"44.2"
geospatial_lat_max	The northernmost latitude, a value between -90 and 90 degrees.	M	"48.5"
geospatial_lat_units	Must conform to udunits . If not specified, then "degrees_north" is assumed	R	"degree_north"
geospatial_lon_min	The westernmost longitude, a value between -180 and 180 degrees.	M	"9.1"
geospatial_lon_max	The easternmost longitude, a value between -180 and 180 degrees.	M	"10.5"
geospatial_lon_units	Must conform to udunits . If not specified, then "degrees_east" is assumed	R	"degree_east"
geospatial_vertical_min	The minimum depth or height of measurements.	M	"0"

geospatial_vertical_max	The maximum depth or height of measurements.	M	"1"
geospatial_vertical_units	Units of depth or height. If not specified, then "m" is assumed.	R	"meters above mean sea level"
geospatial_vertical_positive	Indicates which direction is positive; "up" means that z represents height while a value of "down" (by default if not specified) means that z represents pressure or depth.	R	"up"
geospatial_vertical_resolution	Information about the targeted vertical spacing of points	M	" 25 meters"
grid_resolution	Resolution of the grid.	R	"1 km"
reference_system	EPSG coordinate reference system.	R	"EPSG:4806" (in case of WGS84)
Publication information			
update_interval	Update interval for the file, in ISO 8610 interval format: PnYnMnDTnHnM . Use "void" for data that are not updated on a schedule.	M	"void"
citation	The citation to be used in publications using the dataset, including a reference to the FOCCUS project. When available, the DOI of the data product will be included.	M	"The data were collected and made freely available through the FOCCUS project (EU GA.No. 101133911) and the national programs that contribute to it"
publisher_url	Web address of the institution or of the data publisher.	M	https://zenodo.org/
publisher_institution	Name of the institution that publish the data	R	ZENODO
license	A statement describing the data distribution policy.	M	"This data product is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License"
acknowledgement	A place to acknowledge various types of support for the project that produced this data.	M	"FOCCUS, Funded by the European Union, Grant Agreement No. 101133911 "
Provenance			
date_created	The date the data file was created. Use: ISO8601 standard:"YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ssZ"	M	"2024-09-16T00:30:00Z"
history	Text tracking modifications to original data. Use a separate line for each change, including a	M	"2024-09-16T00:30:00Z data created. 2024-09-17T00:30:00Z data modified. 2024-09-17T00:30:00Z date processed and

	timestamp in ISO8601 format, user's name, type of modification and arguments.		distributed"
processing_level	Processing level and quality control applied to the data. Use: Levels used for data processing	M	"L2"
creator_name	Name (EU suggest to use ORCID) of the main researchers involved in producing the data, or the authors of the publication, in priority order.	R	"0000-0002-6475-5088"
creator_url	Web address of the institution or data publisher.	R	"https://nersc.no"
contributor_name	Names (EU suggest to use ORCID) of any individuals or institutions that contributed to the creation of this data, separated by semicolons.	M	"0000-0002-6475-5088"
contributor_url	The roles of any individuals or institutions that contributed to the creation of this data. Use: DataCite Contributor Type	M	"DataCollector"
contributor_email	The institutional email addresses of any individuals or institutions that contributed to the creation of this data, separated by semi- colons.	M	"mobims@socib.es"
method	The method of production of the original data	M	"Attitude and residual bias correction / CDOP3SiX Geophysical Model Function"
track_id	Globally unique identification for each dataset. Unique product identifier (PID), e.g. including UUID, DOI, ROR, etc. If it is still not available, please add "to be available in FOCCUS D2.2. - 1st version of data"	M	"10.1038/s41597-023-02210-2"
scientific_support_contact	Institutional emails for scientific support	R	"mobims@socib.es"
technical_support_contact	Institutional emails for technical support	R	"datacenter@socib.es"

Annex II: Key performance indicators

Annex II outlines the **Key Performance Indicators** (KPIs) used to monitor progress towards **FOCCUS Objective 1**: "Improve pan-EU innovative coastal observations in response to society and EU policy needs."

As it is included in the Description of Work, these **KPIs** focus on:

- Data traceability and tracking [1 mid-term and 1 final data status and statistics report];
- WP2: Design [Number of releases of data product samples. Percentage of progress in the preparation of data product development]
- WP3: Implementation, production and validation [Number of releases of data product (final version). Percentage of progress in the preparation of data product development] of:
 - 6 operational data products and 1 data product development for **improved coastal observations**;
 - 1 operational data product and 2 data product development for **data fusion**;
 - 2 data products for validation for **satellite calibration and validation**;
 - 1 data product development for **new data processing algorithms**.

Table 27: Number of releases of data product samples . Specific data products and the expected outcomes are detailed in [Table 1](#) of this deliverable.

Products - WP2 Design	Num. data product samples	Progress % of the data product development ⁸
2.1. Improve coastal observations	6 ODP	1 PDPD [at 30%]
2.2. Data fusion	1 ODP	2 PDPD [at 30%]
2.2. Data for satellite Cal/Val	2 DPV	
2.3. New data processing algorithms		1 PDPD [at 30%]
2.3. Data traceability and tracking	1 Mid-term data inventory 1 Mid-term statistics Report	

⁸ Data product development progress is measured as: 30% - Design [D2.1], 70% - Publication [D2.2], 100% - Validation [D3.2]